

Reliable in-Vehicle pErception and decisioN-making in complex environmenTal conditionS

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D.2.3 Vehicle System Hazard Analysis & Risk Assessment

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Contributors	All Task 2.4 partners	Lead Authors	Yogesh Ganesh, APTIV
		Reviewers	Anastasia Bolovinou, ICCS Siddartha Kashgir, WMG

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Author(s)		
First Name	Last Name	Partner
Yogesh	Ganesh	APTIV
Mariat	James Elizebeth	WMG
Bill	Roungas	ICCS
Anthony	Ohazulike	HIT-FR
Alireza	Ahrabian	HIT-UK
Dariu	Gavrila	TUD

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Quality Control		
Role	Who (Partner's short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable Leader	Yogesh Ganesh (APTIV)	30/08/2023
Quality manager	Panagiotis Lytrivis (ICCS)	31/08/2023
Project Coordinator	Angelos Amditis (ICCS)	31/08/2023

Executive Summary

The “D2.3: Vehicle system hazard analysis & risk assessment” deliverable is a public report of the EVENTS project, dealing with the risks and potential hazards associated with each use case by performing a Risk Assessment and Hazard Analysis (HARA) process. The approach taken in this work proposes a hybrid scheme that integrates STPA analysis with classical HARA.

The safety analysis findings are then used to formulate safety goals that are required to be met, in order for each vehicle system to operate safely within its ODD.

Work on Task 2.4 is based on the use case specification including ODD definition (mainly level of automation, road types and required infrastructure), the expected use-case exposure as well as the system architecture provided by the previous tasks.

Acceptance criteria, which are used to measure/assure safety of the intended function (SOTIF) of an autonomous vehicle or advanced driver assistance system (ADAS), are provided for the European roads. These initial performance goals will feed the development work of WP3 (Perception and self-assessment) and WP4 (On-board decision-making for fail-safe automated vehicle motion), where a list of reasonably quantified SOTIF events will be provided based on simulation testing, which in turn will feed the work on vehicle system safety compliance verification on Task T5.3.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	9
2. Methodology	10
2.1 Method 1: Hazard and Operability Study.....	10
2.2 Method 2: Systems-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA)	11
2.3 Integrating STPA steps into ISO26262	12
3. Item Definition: System scope and definition.	13
3.1 Initial Inputs for HARA	13
3.2 STPA Step 1: Define Purpose	14
3.1 STPA Step 2: Model Control Structure	15
4. Vehicle Level Hazard analysis	17
4.1 Functional Decomposition of CAV.....	17
4.2 Functions list with applicable HAZOP Guidewords	18
4.3 Experiments for hazard analysis.....	19
Table 4 : Location and surface condition table.....	19
Table 5 : Weather and traffic condition table.....	20
4.4 Vehicle Operating Modes	20
4.5 STPA Step 3: Identify Unsafe Control Actions (UCA's)	20
5. Risk Assessment – ASIL Rating	22
5.1 Safety goals derived from HARA.....	22
5.2 Assigning Control Actions to ADS Functions	23
6. Safety Analysis	24
6.1 STPA Step 4: Identify Causal Factors	24
6.2 Requirements derived from STPA Analysis	25
7. Functional Safety Concept & Requirements	26
7.1 Activation / Deactivation Functional Safety Concepts	26
7.2 HMI Status Functional Safety Concept	27
7.3 Longitudinal Control Functional Safety Concept.....	27
7.4 Lateral Control Functional Safety Concept.....	29
7.5 Take Over Request & Safe Stop Functional Safety Concept.....	29
7.6 Usage of STPA derived requirements & FSC in EVENTS	30
8. Acceptance Criteria for SOTIF based on Mileage Strategy	31

9. Conclusions33

References..... 34

Annex 1: Model Control Structure 35

Annex 2: STPA Spte 3 36

Annex 3: Hazon-based HARA.....46

Annex 4: STPA Step 454

Annex 5: Safety Requirements 122

List of Tables

Table 1: Identified Losses..... 15

Table 2: Vehicle level hazard table. 15

Table 3: Applicable HAZOP Guidewords for ADS functions. 18

Table 4: Location and surface condition table 19

Table 5: Weather and traffic condition table 20

Table 6: Vehicle operating mode table 20

Table 7: Safety goal summary 22

Table 8: Mapping Control Actions to ADS Functions table 23

Table 9: Failure criticality to safe state transition table 30

Table 10: Acceptance Criteria Calculation 32

List of Figures

Figure 1: HAZOP Steps 10

Figure 2: STPA Steps 11

Figure 3: STPA in ISO26262 Context..... 12

Figure 4: Item Context Diagram 13

Figure 5: EVENTS system architecture diagram 14

Figure 6: Model Control Structure (a larger image is shown in Annex 1) 16

Figure 7: The STPA Step 3..... 17

Figure 8: CAV Functional Decomposition 17

Figure 9: UCA Guideword 21

Figure 10: The Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL) 22

Figure 11: The STPA Step 4..... 24

Figure 12: The Functional Safety Concept & Requirements 26

Figure 13: Activation/Deactivation Safety Concept. 26

Figure 14: HMI Safety concept 27

Figure 15: Longitudinal & Lateral Control Functional Safety Concept 28

Figure 16: EXP6 high-level Full Stack Architecture and Interfaces..... 30

Abbreviations & Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
ACC	Adaptive Cruise Control
AD(F)	Autonomous Driving (Function)
ADS	Autonomous Driving System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AL	Alert Limit
AV	Automated Vehicle
BP	Behavioural Planner
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAV	Connected Automated Vehicle
CPM	Collective Perception Messages
DDT	Dynamic Driving Task
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DM	Decision Making
EC	European Commission
EXPs	Experiments
FIS	Fuzzy Inference System
FoV	Field of View
FSC	Functional Safety Concept
FTP	Fail-degraded Trajectory Planning
GA	Grant Agreement
IR	Integrity Risk
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
I/O	Input(s) / Output(s)
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MRM	Minimum Risk Manoeuvre

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
MOP	Moving Object Prediction
MOT	Multi-Object Tracking
ODD	Operational Design Domain
PE	Position Error
PL	Protection Level
PP	Perception Platform
RADAR	RAdio Detecting And Ranging
REQs	Requirements
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SMD	Safety-mode Decision
SPaT message	Signal Phase and Timing message
SPECs	Specifications
TOR	Take Over Request
TP	Trajectory Planner
TSs	Target Scenarios
UCs	Use Cases
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Assuring safety is important in autonomous vehicles. The safety related to autonomous vehicles can be primarily viewed from two perspectives [6]: the functional safety (FuSa) and the safety of the intended functionality (SOTIF). While FuSa ensures the system has an acceptable risk with respect to malfunctions of electrical and electronic components, SOTIF ensures the system has an acceptable risk with respect to functional insufficiencies and performance limitations. SOTIF also considers expected system misuse, touching on cybersecurity aspects; however, such aspects are considered out of the project focus and will not be covered by this work.

With the growing complexity of automotive systems and the integration of advanced technologies, ensuring functional safety is of utmost importance. ISO 26262 [1], the international standard for functional safety in the automotive industry, provides a structured framework to address these safety challenges. In ISO 26262, the concept of *HARA* (Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment) is introduced for system safety assessment during the concept phase of the system. HARA is an integral part of the functional safety process since it serves as the foundation for identifying potential hazards and assessing their associated risks. It involves a rigorous examination of potential failure modes, their causes, and the severity of their consequences on vehicle occupants, other road users, and the environment. Once HARA is completed, functional safety requirements are created and all the findings are aggregated into a functional safety concept. Works that augment HARA with scenario-based analysis or replace HARA with alternatives more suitable for AD systems have recently appeared [7].

2. Methodology

This project combines two analysis methods, namely HAZOP and STPA to generate a list of hazards and based on this, the safety analysis results.

2.1 Method 1: Hazard and Operability Study

HAZOP (Hazard and Operability Study) is a systematic and structured approach used in industries such as chemical, petrochemical, and manufacturing to identify potential hazards and operability issues in processes, systems, and equipment. The classical HAZOP approach has several advantages:

1. Comprehensive Hazard Identification
2. Structured and Systematic
3. Team Collaboration
4. Risk Assessment
5. Early Identification of Hazards

Figure 1 illustrates the analytical steps of the HAZOP study.

Figure 1: HAZOP Steps

This study applies the HAZOP study steps shown in Figure 1 as follows:

1. Define the system of study and the scope of the analysis.
2. List all the functions that the system components are designed to perform.
3. For each of the identified functions, apply a set of guidewords [8] that describe the various ways in which the function may deviate from its design intent.
4. Identified malfunctions from relevant guideword for each function is then analyzed with applicable scenarios to document the context of malfunction.
5. Severity, Exposure, Controllability [9] is then analyzed for step 4.
6. Top level Safety goals are derived to be fulfilled by the system design.

2.2 Method 2: Systems-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA)

The STPA is a top-down system engineering approach to system safety that guides safety managers and analysts in the identification of a migration toward states of higher risk [11] and addresses more types of hazards and treats safety as a dynamic control problem rather than an individual component failure. STPA also addresses types of hazardous causes in the absence of failure [12]. In STPA, the system is modelled as a dynamic control structure, where proper controls and communications in the system ensure the desired outcome for emergent properties, such as safety. In the STPA framework, a system will not enter a hazardous state unless an unsafe control action is issued by a controller, or a control action needed to maintain safety is not issued. The STPA steps are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: STPA Steps

2.3 Integrating STPA steps into ISO26262

The absence of a risk assessment phase in the STPA analysis method represents a notable omission, as this step plays a crucial role in determining the safety integrity allocation on system elements. In Figure 3, the procedures for incorporating STPA into the ISO26262 [REF ISO] process methodology are presented.

Figure 3: STPA in ISO26262 Context

By merging the traditional HAZOP process with STPA, we have enhanced our safety analysis approach, making it more tailored for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs).

3. Item Definition: System scope and definition.

The System Scope refers to defining the boundaries and extent of the automotive safety system under consideration. This involves specifying the components, functions, and interfaces that are within the scope of the safety assessment.

Figure 4: Item Context Diagram

3.1 Initial Inputs for HARA

Analysis Assumptions on CAV

- Autonomy vehicle level – L3 system (Driver hands off).
- ODD as defined to include all experiments for the EVENTS Use Cases 1, 2 & 3 [14] [15].

- Vehicle equipped with automatic gear, wiper and headlights.
- Autonomous mode intended for forward motion only.

Analysis Assumptions on Driver

- Driver with valid driving license.
- Driver shall remain attentive and able to take back control in time when requested by the Autonomy Function.

Figure 5: EVENTS system architecture diagram

3.2 STPA Step 1: Define Purpose

Purpose: Identify Losses

An approach to identifying losses involves:

1. Identify the stakeholders, e.g. Users, producers, customers, operators, etc.
2. Stakeholders identify their “stake” in the system. What do they value? For example, human life, fleet of useable aircraft, electrical power generation, transportation, etc. What are their goals? For example, maintain a fleet of useable aircraft, provide transportation, provide medical treatment, provide electrical power generation, etc.
3. Translate each value or goal into a loss.

Identified list of losses:

L-1: Loss of life or injury to people

L-2: Loss or damage to vehicle

L-3: Loss or damage to objects outside the vehicle

**The focus of this safety analysis will be to cover loss of life or injury to driver, passenger or pedestrians and other losses have been excluded.*

Losses	
L-1	Loss of life or injury to driver, passengers, or pedestrians

Table 1: Identified Losses

A hazard is a system state or set of conditions that, together with a set of worst-case environmental conditions, will lead to a loss.

Vehicle-Level Hazards:	Hazard Description	Link to Losses
H-1	CAV fails to maintain minimum separation with or collides with vulnerable road users.	L-1
H-2	CAV fails to maintain minimum separation with or collides laterally with static/dynamic objects.	L-1
H-3	CAV fails to maintain minimum separation with or collides longitudinally with static/dynamic objects.	L-1
H-4	CAV fails to follow traffic signs / rules.	L-1
H-5	CAV enters an uncontrolled state.	L-1
<i>Note: Vulnerable road users can include pedestrians, cyclists, horse riders, motorcyclists and people using mobility scooters.</i>		

Table 2: Vehicle level hazard table.

3.1 STPA Step 2: Model Control Structure

The control structure represents how the system is controlled or managed. It includes the controllers, operators, and automated control elements that influence the system's behavior. In Figure 6, the **RED** downward arrows represent the control actions and the **BLUE** upward arrows indicate the feedback signals. The UCA (unsafe control action) Guideword is applied to each control action and relevant hazard is documented in STPA Step 3.

Figure 6: Model Control Structure (a larger image is shown in Annex 1)

4. Vehicle Level Hazard analysis

Vehicle Level Hazard Analysis involves systematically identifying potential safety risks in a vehicle's design and operation, assessing the severity and probability of these hazards, and implementing measures to mitigate them. This process helps ensure that vehicles are engineered with a strong focus on safety, reducing the risk of accidents and enhancing overall road safety. This activity is performed at a vehicle level and the top-level safety goals are derived. The subsystems will inherit the relevant safety goals and ASIL targets.

Figure 7: The STPA Step 3

4.1 Functional Decomposition of CAV.

Functional decomposition of a Level 3 (CAV) autonomous system involves breaking down the system's capabilities and functions into distinct components that work together to enable the vehicle to operate autonomously.

Figure 8: CAV Functional Decomposition

4.2 Functions list with applicable HAZOP Guidewords

		HAZOP Guide Word			
	ADS Function List	No /Loss /Missing	Incorrect	Unintended	Insufficient
1	ADS Activation	x	x	x	Not Applicable
2	ADS De-activation	x	x	x	Not Applicable
3	ADS Lateral Control	x	x	x	x
4	ADS Longitudinal Control (Acceleration & Braking)	x	x	x	x
5	ADS Take Over Request (CAV initiated)	x	x	x	Not Applicable
6	ADS Minimum Risk Maneuver	x	x	x	Not Applicable
7	ADS Status (Active/Inactive)	x	x	Not Applicable	Not Applicable

ADS – Autonomous Driving System

Table 3: Applicable HAZOP Guidewords for ADS functions.

4.3 Experiments for hazard analysis.

The list of experiments provides Locations, Road & Weather conditions and Traffic and people considerations [14] and its relevant combinations, which are included in the HARA analysis. Namely, the EVENTS experiments are:

EXP1: Interaction with VRUs under complex urban environment. (*HARA Analysis on Urban roads with VRU's and adverse weather conditions*)

EXP2: Re-establish platoon formation after splitting due to roundabout. (*HARA Analysis on Urban roads*)

EXP3: Self-assessment and reliability of perception data with complementary V2X data in complex urban environments. (*HARA Analysis on Urban roads*)

EXP4: Decision making for motion planning when faced with roadworks, unmarked lanes and narrow roads with assistance from perception self-assessment. (*HARA Analysis on Urban roads & Highway with Missing lane information and Construction zone*)

EXP5: Decision making for motion planning when entering a jammed highway. (*HARA Analysis on Highways with varying traffic conditions*)

EXP6: Small object detection at a far range in adverse weather conditions. (*HARA Analysis on Highways with Static Objects in lane*)

EXP7: Localization/perception self-assessment and other vehicles' behaviour prediction under adverse weather or adverse road conditions. (*HARA Analysis on Urban and highway roads with adverse weather conditions*)

The consolidated list to perform HARA for all experiments is tabulated below.

Location		Surface Condition
Road type	Road layout	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Two way driving non-divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)
	Missing lanes	
	Construction zone	

Table 4: Location and surface condition table

Weather Conditions	Traffic and people	
	Traffic Condition	Static Objects
Normal condition	No Traffic - Free Drive	No Obstruction in Lane
Rain	Slow moving traffic < 10kmph	Obstruction in Lane
Snow	Traffic Standstill	
Dense Fog		

Table 5: Weather and traffic condition table

4.4 Vehicle Operating Modes

CAV Mode	Description	Driving Authority
Manual Mode	Driver performing dynamic driving task.	Driver
Autonomy Active ADS	CAV performing dynamic driving task.	CAV
Take Over Request	CAV performs dynamic driving for short duration until driver takes over.	CAV -> Driver
Minimum Risk Maneuver	CAV performs stop in lane maneuver with gradual deceleration in the absence of driver take over.	CAV

Table 6: Vehicle operating mode table

4.5 STPA Step 3: Identify Unsafe Control Actions (UCA's)

From the control structure each down arrow coloured in RED is a control action. The UCAs (Unsafe Control Actions) which are control actions that, in a particular context and worst-case environment, will lead to a hazard are documented in STPA Step-3.

Figure 4. Guidewords for UCAs

Figure 9: UCA Guideword

The detailed STPA Step 3 can be found in Annex 2.

5. Risk Assessment – ASIL Rating

Risk Assessment is a quantitative assessment of the risk associated with each hazard. Risk is typically calculated as the product of the likelihood (probability) of an event and the severity (consequences) of that event. ISO 26262 [1] defines a specific Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL) scale (ASIL A, B, C, or D) to categorize the risk level.

Figure 10: The Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL)

The detailed HAZOP-based HARA can be found in Annex 3.

5.1 Safety goals derived from HARA

No	Safety Goal	ASIL	Responsible Function
1	Ensure ADS status is correctly reported to the driver	D	ADS Status (Active/Inactive)
2	Prevent control not given back to the driver when requested	D	ADS Take Over Request (Driver Take Over)
3	Prevent ADS use outside of ODD	D	ADS Activation / De-ADS Activation
4	Prevent insufficient/unintended steering.	D	ADS Lateral Control
5	Prevent unintended braking.	C	ADS Longitudinal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
6	Prevent loss or insufficient braking.	D	ADS Longitudinal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
7	Prevent unintended acceleration.	D	ADS Longitudinal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
8	Always activate brake lights when brakes are activated.	C	Vehicle Body/Chassis domain
9	Ensure safe stop in case of no driver take over	D	ADS Minimum Risk Maneuver

Table 7: Safety goal summary

5.2 Assigning Control Actions to ADS Functions

Control Action	From	To	Responsible Function
HMIEnableAD	Driver	AutonomousDrive Controller	ADS Status
HMIDisableAD			
DriverBrakeRequest	Driver	VehicleMotion Controller	ADS Take Over Request (Manual Drive / Driver Override)
DriverSteerRequest			
DriverThrottleRequest			
ADSBrakeRequest	AutonomousDrive Controller	VehicleMotion Controller	ADS Longitudnal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
ADSSteerRequest			ADS Lateral Control
ADSThrottleRequest			ADS Longitudnal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
BrakeRequest	VehicleMotion Controller	VehicleActuators	- General Body domain
SteerRequest			
ThrottleRequest			

Table 8: Mapping Control Actions to ADS Functions table

6. Safety Analysis

After the unsafe control actions have been identified, the next step is to identify loss scenarios. Two types of loss scenarios must be considered:

- a. Why would Unsafe Control Actions occur?
- b. Why would control actions be improperly executed or not executed, leading to hazards?

Figure 11: The STPA Step 4

There are four general reasons why a controller might provide (or not provide) a control action that is unsafe:

- Failures involving the controller (for physical controllers).
- Inadequate control algorithm.
- Unsafe control input (from another controller).
- Inadequate process model.
- Hazards can be caused by UCAs, but they can also be caused without a UCA if control actions are improperly executed or not executed. To create these scenarios, we must consider factors that affect the control path as well as factors that affect the controlled process.

The identification of Causal Factor type, Requirements to Prevent & Detect the Causal Factors is documented below.

6.1 STPA Step 4: Identify Causal Factors

The STPA Step 4 can be found in Annex 4.

6.2 Requirements derived from STPA Analysis

STPA being a systematic approach considers safety as an emergent problem and analyses the complex interactions within the social–technical systems. This kind of approach is suitable for SOTIF issues **Error! Reference source not found..**

In STPA Step 4, we have analyzed known limitations of system components to derive causal scenarios from those limitations that could potentially result in vehicle-level hazards. The Causal Factor analysis which also contains SOTIF triggering events has been grouped into ODD, Driver, Sensors, V2X, Self-Assessment, HMI, AutonomousDriveController, MAPS, VehicleMotionController and can be found in Annex 5.

Also, in Annex 5, the Mitigation strategies for these triggering events such as design decision (mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous inputs) and functional limitation (notification to the driver) have been identified.

7. Functional Safety Concept & Requirements

The Functional Safety Concept (FSC) is a crucial aspect of ISO 26262 [1]. The FSC provides a high-level overview of how functional safety will be achieved in a particular system or component. Six FSCs are considered in this report and are analyzed through a simplified system diagram and a list of safety requirements.

Figure 12: The Functional Safety Concept & Requirements

7.1 Activation / Deactivation Functional Safety Concepts

The Activation / Deactivation Functional Safety Concept addresses SG-03 (Prevent ADS use outside of ODD). When ADS is in Available Mode, it keeps evaluating constantly the ODD and ego vehicle condition and road type. With the help of Figure 13, a list of requirements has been defined as follows:

Figure 13: Activation/Deactivation Safety Concept.

- The ODD Determination block shall prevent the operation of ADS outside its ODD by using information provided by various vehicle sub-systems.
- Map info shall provide Country and Road type information.

- Sensing and Perception shall provide Traffic Signs, Lane situations, Road Situations, Traffic Situations and Extreme Weather conditions.

7.2 HMI Status Functional Safety Concept

The Activation/HMI Status Functional Safety Concept addresses SG-01 (Ensure ADS status is correctly reported to the driver). With the help of Figure 14, a list of requirements has been defined as follows:

Figure 14: HMI Safety concept

- ADS shall compute the correct ADS activation status.
- Failure: avoid setting ADS active when ADS is not active.
- HMI & Infotainment shall indicate to the driver ADS active only when "ADS ACTIVE" is set by ADS System.
- Recommend to use a graphical visualization and / or a textual description

7.3 Longitudinal Control Functional Safety Concept

The Longitudinal Control Functional Safety Concept addresses SG-5, SG-6, SG-7 covering unintended braking on system limit, loss or insufficient braking, and unintended acceleration while ADS is operating.

Figure 15: Longitudinal & Lateral Control Functional Safety Concept

The safety integrity of the longitudinal control request is provided by ADS System with 2 independent channels (Primary and Secondary Trajectory generation). Two operational modes are considered:

1. **Nominal Mode**

- Primary longitudinal Request is ASIL B(D).
- Secondary longitudinal Request is ASIL B(D).
- Sufficient independence between Primary trajectory generation and Secondary. trajectory generation shall be demonstrated.
- Trajectory Validator and selection (between both) is ASIL D. When ADS is Active Control, it shall detect safety relevant obstacle and provide its correct attributes (Position, Long/Lat Speed, Long/Lat Accel,).
- In case of conflict between both trajectory, Initiate TOR apply predefined deceleration profile and maintain the lateral control. Where conflict is assumed to be:
 - One trajectory requesting deceleration and second requesting acceleration.
 - Both trajectories requesting different deceleration values. The conflict thresholds need to be tuned.

2. Fault Handling Mode

- On detection of fault impacting the Primary Longitudinal Control Request Integrity with respect to No/insufficient deceleration, Primary channel shall initiate a Take Over Request.
- On detection of fault impacting the Secondary Longitudinal Control Request Integrity with respect to No/insufficient deceleration, Secondary channel shall initiate a Take Over Request.

7.4 Lateral Control Functional Safety Concept

The Lateral Control Functional Safety Concept addresses SG-04 (Prevent insufficient/unintended steering). The safety integrity of the lateral control request is provided by ADS System with 2 independent channel trajectories. To ensure the sufficient independence between both trajectories, 2 different sources are used for the perception of Ego Lanes:

- Source 1: Camera.
- Source 2: LIDAR / Surround Camera AND Predicted trajectory Lane based on Surrounding Object as lead Vehicle, Adjacent Vehicles, Road Boundaries (Barriers, Edges).

ASIL D: Deviation of more than 50 cm with high yaw rate change (In Annex 3 - ADS Lateral Control).

ASIL B: Deviation of more than 50 cm with low yaw rate change (In Annex 3 - ADS Lateral Control).

In case of conflict between Primary and Secondary trajectories, Initiate TOR apply predefined deceleration profile and maintain the lateral control (Last known best values). Primary & Secondary Channel shall detect Lane markings with Source 1 (Camera) and Source 2 and provide its correct attributes.

Fault magnitude: inaccuracy of +/-50 cm.

7.5 Take Over Request & Safe Stop Functional Safety Concept

Take over request is initiated by the CAV when it can no longer perform the required DDT (Dynamic driving task). Take Over Request FSC addresses SG-2 (Prevent control not given back to the driver when requested) and SG-9 (Ensure safe stop in case of no driver take over). Driver actions on steering and braking has the highest priority over ADS request. Transition to safe stop shall be performed depending on failure category as described in [Table 9](#).

Initial Operating Mode	Failure Categories	ADS capabilities after Failure	Transition to safe state
Available / Standby	Any Failure	-	Feature Disabled
Active Control	Low critical failures	Vehicle is able to maintain follow Lead vehicle/Lane (including collision mitigation)	Comfort Handover- Handover period of 30s and to stop the vehicle within 15sec.
Active Control	High critical failures	Vehicle is able to stop-in-Lane Only	Emergency Deceleration to stop in lane

Table 9: Failure criticality to safe state transition table

7.6 Usage of STPA derived requirements & FSC in EVENTS

This section explains, using an example, the methodology for usage of derived safety concept and the STPA requirements for the individual experiments.

EVENTS module owners shall select the applicable safety concept from Section 6 that is relevant for their experiment. For example, in EXP6 (*Small object detection at a far range in adverse weather conditions*), as illustrated in Figure 11, the focus is only on Sensing & Perception and Decision/Motion Planning.

Figure 16: EXP6 high-level Full Stack Architecture and Interfaces

EXP6 shall apply the Longitudinal & Lateral Control Functional Safety Concepts and the requirements from STPA analysis (Section 6.2) from Sensors & Perception, AutonomousDriveController, and MAPS.

8. Acceptance Criteria for SOTIF based on Mileage Strategy

Acceptance criteria are the most important metrics used to measure/assure safety of the intended function (SOTIF) of an autonomous vehicle or advanced driver assistance system (ADAS) [16]. Mileage refers to the distance a vehicle can cover using one gallon or liter of fuel or per one charge cycle. Considering a car's operating speed and mileage, there is a limited amount of time or distance it can travel in a given year. Within this mileage strategy [10], we utilize this time or distance to establish Acceptance Criteria values.

Factors to Consider for calculating Acceptance Criteria with Mileage Strategy:

Average Vehicle Speed: In the context of the mileage strategy, it is crucial to monitor the average speed of a vehicle during its Operation Design Domain (ODD). This is because urban, rural, and highway mileages can vary significantly for vehicles. Furthermore, when a vehicle operates at a low average speed within its ODD, there's a limit to the number of miles it can cover even with extended hours of operation. This information helps us assess whether we require more test fleet vehicles or simply need to adjust the planned timeline for mileage accumulation.

Crash Data: Similar to the operational lifetime strategy, obtaining crash data for the mileage strategy may not always be straightforward. Instead, we may need to estimate the number of crashes by considering the ODD or the expected average accidents per km within the ODD. This estimation is essential for calculating Acceptance Criteria (AC) [2][3][4][5].

ODD Factors: Just like in other strategies, ODD factors are significant in the context of the mileage strategy. Regardless of the total potential achievable mileage by the vehicles, insufficient coverage of the intended ODD factors could compromise Safety of the Intended Function (SOTIF) assurance.

Table 10 can be used to calculate the Acceptance criteria based on the mileage strategy.

9. Conclusions

In conclusion, the completion of the D2.3 deliverable represents a significant milestone in ensuring the safety and reliability of our autonomous driving system. By employing both classical Hazard and Operability (HAZOP) analysis and the System-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) approach, one of the notable achievements of this deliverable is the clear definition of safety goals and safety requirements. These are essential components for guiding the development and evaluation of our autonomous driving system.

The tabulation of safety requirements into distinct categories, including ODD (Operational Design Domain), Sensors, Driver Interaction, and AVstack (Autonomous Drive Controller), provides a structured framework for addressing specific safety concerns within each area. Furthermore, the Functional Safety Concept (FSC) outlined in this deliverable illustrates how we intend to achieve system-level safety, by outlining the strategies and measures to mitigate identified risks.

In the future, our steps will involve these safety concept and safety requirements to be accepted by experiment leaders and implemented during the implementation phase of the project (WP5).

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Annex 1: Model Control Structure

Annex 2: STPA Step 3

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon				
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards		
HMIEnableAD	Driver	Autonomous DriveController	UCA-1.1.1	HMIEnableAD not provided when the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path, the driver intends to activate ADS and has stopped performing the DDT. <i>Note: The Driver may assume that they have already provided it, but the request may not have been actually sent/received by the AutonomousDriveController due to various reasons.</i>	H-1,3,5	UCA-1.2.1	HMIEnableAD Provided Incorrectly when CAV is outside its ODD (Eg: heavy snow/rain, poor lighting/poor visibility, a significant object has been detected but not classified and collision is imminent) and Driver has stopped performing the DDT.	H-2,3,5							UCA-1.5.1	HMIEnableAD Provided too late when the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle or VRU in its path, the driver intends to activate ADS and has stopped performing the DDT.	H-1,3,5							N/A - Discrete signal/command.	N/A -Discrete signal/command.
			UCA-1.1.2	HMIEnableAD not provided when the CAV is operating on a motorway, another vehicle is cutting into CAV path, the driver intends to activate ADS and has stopped performing the DDT.	H-3,5	UCA-1.2.2	HMIEnableAD Provided Incorrectly when there is a severe ADS/CAV failure and the driver has stopped performing the DDT.	H-5																	
HMIDisableAD	Driver	Autonomous DriveController	UCA-2.1.1	HMIDisableAD not provided when the ADS is enabled, Driver is not able to perform the DDT, the CAV is getting close to a significant obstacle or VRU in its path	H-1,3,5				UCA-2.3.1	Driver provides HMIDisableAD when ADS is enabled, the CAV is within its ODD, there are static obstacles, dynamic obstacles and VRUs in the close vicinity of the CAV and the Driver is not performing the DDT.	H-1,2,3,5				UCA-2.5.1	HMIDisableAD provided too late when the ADS is enabled, Driver is not able to perform the DDT, the CAV is getting close to a significant obstacle or VRU in its path	H-1,3,5							N/A - Discrete signal/command.	N/A -Discrete signal/command.
			UCA-2.1.2	HMIDisableAD not provided when the ADS	H-1,5																				

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon			
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	
DriverBrakeRequest	Driver	VehicleMotionController	UCA-3.1.1	Driver does not provide DriverBrakeRequest when ADS is disabled and the CAV is about to collide with a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path.	H-1,3										UCA-3.5.1	Driver provides DriverBrakeRequest too late when ADS is disabled and the CAV is about to collide with a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path.	H-1,3							
			UCA-3.1.2	Driver does not provide DriverBrakeRequest when ADS is disabled and the CAV is approaching a red traffic light signal.	H-4											UCA-3.5.2	Driver provides DriverBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, there is a takeover request and a load is falling from a truck ahead.	H-3						
DriverSteerRequest	Driver	VehicleMotionController	UCA-4.1.1	Driver does not provide DriverSteerRequest when ADS is disabled at Night in cold and wet weather (rain) and CAV is in a situation where steering is required (e.g. maneuvering a roundabout, bend/curve).	H-2,3				UCA-4.3.1	Driver provides DriverSteerRequest when ADS is disabled and there are vehicles beside the CAV in adjacent lanes or CAV is close to the central reservation	H-2					UCA-4.5.1	Driver provides DriverSteerRequest too late when ADS is disabled, a VRU suddenly appears, moving towards the path of the CAV, there are no obstacles on the adjacent lane and maximum deceleration is insufficient to avoid a collision with the VRU.	H-3						

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon		
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards
DriverThrottleRequest	Driver	VehicleMotionController				UCA-5.2.1	Driver provides incorrect DriverThrottleRequest when ADS is disabled and the CAV is in a situation where optimal acceleration is needed(moving down a slope and there are leading vehicles in the path.)	H-2,3	UCA-5.3.1	Driver provides DriverThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled and the CAV is approaching an obstacle in its path. <i>Note: The driver override in this case may lead to collision</i>	H-3												
									UCA-5.3.2	Driver provides DriverThrottleRequest when ADS is disabled and the current speed is above the maximum limit for the current zone/road	H-4												
			UCA-6.1.1	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest during Night time when the CAV is operating on a motorway /jammed highway ramp/dense urban road,ADS is enabled,weather conditions are adverse (rain/snow/fog/ice on road) and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle/VRU in its path.	H-1,3	UCA-6.2.1	Autonomous DriveController provides insufficient ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled , the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path and there is an imminent collision risk.	H-1,3						UCA-6.5.1	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, the CAV is operating on a motorway /jammed highway ramp/dense urban road, at Night, weather conditions are adverse(rain/snow/fog/ice on road) and there is a significant obstacle (eg: parked vehicle, decelerating lead vehicle, road works, blocked lane etc.)or a VRU in the CAV path.	H-1,3					UCA-6.7.1	AutonomousDriveController stops providing ADSBrakeRequest too soon during the Night time when the CAV is operating on a motorway /highway/dense urban road, ADS is enabled, weather conditions are adverse(rain/snow/fog/ice on the road), the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle/VRU in its path and an imminent collision risk prevails.	H-1,2,3

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon			
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	
ADSBrakeRequest	Autonomous DriveController	VehicleMotionController	UCA-6.1.2	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV is approaching a roundabout, there are no lead vehicles and there are vehicles approaching from the right.	H-2,4	UCA-6.2.2	Autonomous DriveController provides insufficient ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled and the current speed of the CAV is too high to navigate around an approaching sharp bend (narrow curve radii).	H-2,3																
			UCA-6.1.3	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV is operating on a motorway/highway/dense urban road, there is a malfunction/reduction of accuracy of the Localization, and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle/VRU in its path.	H-1,3						UCA-6.3.1	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, there are vehicles following the CAV closely behind and there are no obstacles ahead. <i>Note: This may lead to a rear obstacle collision.</i>	H-3											
			UCA-6.5.2	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, the CAV is approaching a roundabout, there are no lead vehicles and there are vehicles approaching from the right	H-2,3,4																			
			UCA-6.5.3	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled and CAV is approaching a red traffic light.	H-3,4																			
			UCA-6.7.2	AutonomousDriveController stops providing ADSBrakeRequest too soon when ADS is enabled and the current vehicle speed is still high for the situation (Eg: manoeuvring a sharp bend/ turn, approaching a slow speed zone with roadworks, decelerating lead vehicle, etc.)																				

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon				
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards		
ADSSteerRequest	Autonomous DriveController	VehicleMotionController	UCA-7.1.1	Autonomous DriveController does not provide ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, there is a significant obstacle(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works or special vehicles) or a suddenly appearing VRU in the lane of the CAV and adjacent lanes are available /free of obstacles	H-1,3,4	UCA-7.2.1	Autonomous DriveController provides incorrect ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, weather conditions are adverse (heavy rain/snow/fo g/ice on the road), the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/c urve and is too close to the border.	H-2,3							UCA-7.5.1	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSSteerRequest too late when ADS is enabled, there is a significant obstacle(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works), or a VRU in the lane of the CAV and adjacent lanes are available /free of obstacles	H-1,3					UCA-7.7.1	Autonomous DriveController stops providing ADSSteerRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, there is a significant obstacle(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works) or a VRU in the lane of the CAV, adjacent lanes are available /free of obstacles and an imminent collision risk prevails.	H-1,2,3	
			UCA-7.1.2	Autonomous DriveController does not provide ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve and is too close to the border.	H-2,3	UCA-7.2.2	Autonomous DriveController provides incorrect ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, there is a VRU(cyclist/horse-rider/mobility scooter user) in the lane of travel of the CAV and the CAV is performing an overtake maneuver.	H-2	UCA-7.3.1	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSSteerRequest (lane change) when ADS is enabled, there is an insignificant(overdriveable) obstacle(eg:leaf , mud) in the CAV path and there are vehicles in adjacent lanes.	H-2					UCA-7.5.2	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSSteerRequest too late when ADS is enabled, a VRU suddenly appears, moving towards the path of the CAV, there are no obstacles on the adjacent lane and maximum deceleration is insufficient to avoid a collision with the VRU.	H-3		UCA-7.6.1	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSSteerRequest too long when ADS is enabled, weather conditions are adverse (heavy rain/snow/fo g/ice on the road), the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/c urve and is too close to the border.	H-2	UCA-7.7.2	Autonomous DriveController stops providing ADSSteerRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, the CAV is continuing to maneuver a sharp turn/bend/curve.	H-2,3
			UCA-7.1.3	Autonomous DriveController does not provide ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled and the CAV is merging onto the main road from a ramp.	H-2,3	UCA-7.2.3	Autonomous DriveController provides incorrect(excessive) ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, lane markings are faded/absent and there are obstacles adjacent to the CAV.	H-2																	

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon			
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	
						UCA-8.2.3	Autonomous DriveController provides incorrect(insufficient) ADSThrottle Request when ADS is enabled, the CAV current speed is far below the maximum speed for the current zone of operation and there are vehicles approaching from behind. <i>Note: This may lead to rear-end collision</i>	H-3,4	UCA-8.3.3	Autonomous DriveController provides ADSThrottleRequest when the CAV is approaching a slower speed zone and there are obstacles(eg: decelerating vehicles) ahead.	H-4,3													
BrakeRequest	VehicleMotionController	VehicleActuators	UCA-9.1.1	VehicleMotionController does not provide BrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a brake request and the CAV is in a situation where deceleration is required(approaching a slow speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.).	H-1,2,3,4	UCA-9.2.1	VehicleMotionController provides incorrect BrakeRequest when Driver has provided an override and the CAV is in a situation where deceleration is required(approaching a slow speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.).	H-1,2,3,4,5	UCA-9.3.1	VehicleMotionController provides incorrect BrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, no brake request has been issued by the Autonomous Drive Controller or the Driver, there are no obstacles or VRUs ahead of the CAV and there are vehicles following closely behind.	H-3					UCA-9.5.1	VehicleMotionController provides BrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a brake request and the CAV is in a situation where deceleration is required(approaching a slow speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.).	H-1,2,3,4				UCA-9.7.1	VehicleMotionController stops providing BrakeRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a brake request and the CAV continues to be in a situation where deceleration is required(approaching a slow speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.).	H-1,2,3,4

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon		
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards
SteerRequest	VehicleMotionController	VehicleActuators	UCA-10.1.1	VehicleMotionController does not provide SteerRequest when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a steer request and the CAV is in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV, maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a MRM etc.)	H-1,2,3	UCA-10.2.1	VehicleMotionController provides incorrect SteerRequest when Driver has provided an override and the CAV is in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV, maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve etc.)	H-1,2,3,5	UCA-10.3.1	VehicleMotionController provides SteerRequest when ADS is enabled, no steer request has been issued by the Autonomous Drive Controller or the Driver, and there are vehicles or VRUs in adjacent lanes.	H-1,2				UCA-10.5.1	VehicleMotionController provides SteerRequest too late when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a steer request and the CAV is in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV and adjacent lanes are free; maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a	H-1,2,3	UCA-10.6.1	VehicleMotionController provides SteerRequest too long when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a steer request, weather conditions are adverse (heavy rain, snow, fog or ice on road) and the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a MRM etc	H-2	UCA-10.7.1	VehicleMotionController stops providing SteerRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, ADS has issued a steer request and the CAV is still in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV, maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a MRM etc.)	H-1,2,3
ThrottleRequest	VehicleMotionController	VehicleActuators	UCA-11.1.1	VehicleMotionController does not provide ThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a throttle request and there are vehicles approaching from behind.	H-3	UCA-11.2.1	VehicleMotionController provides an incorrect ThrottleRequest (excessive) when the Driver has provided an override, weather conditions are adverse (rain/snow/fog/ice on the road), the CAV is very close to the road border and there are lead vehicles on the CAV path.	H-2,3	UCA-11.3.1	VehicleMotionController provides ThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled, no throttle request has been issued by the Autonomous Drive Controller or the Driver, and the CAV is approaching an obstacle (eg: stationary vehicle, blocked lane of travel, decelerating lead vehicle, vehicle cutting in, etc.) or a VRU or red traffic light sign in its path.	H-1,3,4				UCA-11.5.1	VehicleMotionController provides ThrottleRequest too late when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a throttle request, there are no obstacles ahead of the CAV and there are vehicles following closely behind.	H-3				UCA-11.7.1	VehicleMotionController stops providing ThrottleRequest too soon when ADS is enabled and providing ADSThrottleRequest, there are no obstacles ahead of the CAV and there are vehicles following closely behind.	H-3

Control Action	From	To	Not provided			Provided Incorrectly			Provided but Not Needed			Provided too Early			Provided too Late			Provided too Long			Stopped Providing too Soon							
			ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards	ID	Description	Hazards					
DynamicPath VerificationResponse <i>Note: Requirements on Dynamic Path Verification around an obstacle are limited. Hence the scope of UCAs is also limited.</i>	Remote Operator	Autonomous DriveController	UCA-12.1.1	RemoteOperator or does not provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received and verified and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3	UCA-12.2.1	RemoteOperator provides DynamicPathVerificationResponse incorrectly when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received but not verified or verified incorrectly and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3				UCA-12.4.1	RemoteOperator provides DynamicPathVerificationResponse too early when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received but not verified and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3	UCA-12.5.1	RemoteOperator provides DynamicPathVerificationResponse too late when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received and verified and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3							N/A - Discrete signal/command.			N/A - Discrete signal/command.	

Annex 3: HAZOP-based HARA

Location		Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic and people		Malfunctioning Behaviour
Road type	Road layout				Traffic Condition	Static Objects	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	Manual Mode	No Traffic - Free Drive	No Obstruction in Lane	No ADS Activation
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)	Rain	Autonomy Active ADS	Slow moving traffic < 10kmph	Obstruction in Lane	Unintended ADS Activation
	Missing lanes		Snow	Take Over Request - MRM	Traffic Standstill		No ADS Deactivation (outside ODD)
	Construction zone		Dense Fog				Unintended ADS Deactivation
							Incorrect ADS Lateral Control
							Loss of ADS Lateral Control
							Unintended Acceleration (ADS Longitudnal Control)
							No Acceleration (ADS Longitudnal Control)
							Unintended Deceleration (ADS Longitudnal Control)
							Insufficient deceleration (ADS Longitudnal Control)
							No deceleration (ADS Longitudnal Control)
							No ADS Take Over Request
							Unintended ADS Take Over Request
							No ADS Minium Risk Manuve Trigger
							Unintended
							ADS Minium Risk Manuver Trigger
							No ADS Display Status
							Incorrect ADS Display Status

CAV Mode	Description	Driving Authority
Manual Mode	Driver performing dynamic driving task.	Driver
Autonomy Active ADS	CAV performing dynamic driving task.	CAV
Take Over Request	CAV performs dynamic driving until driver takes over.	CAV
Minium Risk Manuver	CAV performs dynamic driving until driver takes over.	CAV

No ADS Activation													
Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severity Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	Manual Mode	Any	E4	Manual Driving - E4	S0	No Severity in case of No ADS Activation	C1	Driver Still in control	Not Safety Relevant	Driver requests ADS Activation from manual drive mode, No Activation of ADS and driver still in control.

Incorrect ADS Activation													
Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severity Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	Manual Mode	Any	E4	Manual Driving - E4 outside ODD	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	Driver requests ADS Activation from manual drive mode outside ODD (Operating Design Domain), ADS is Activated . Risk of collision when ADS Activated outside of ODD.

No ADS De-Activation													
Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severity Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Driver not able to De-activate the ADS Feature	D	Driver requests ADS De-Activation from ADSActive mode , Driver not able to take back vehicle control

Incorrect ADS De-Activation													
Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severity Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S0	No Severity in case of Incorrect ADS Activation with Take over Request	C1	Driver can take back control in the TOR time , or MRM will be performed.	QM	Driver takes back control in TOR time.
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	No Take Over Request , Driver not in control of vehicle when ADS is De-activated	D	Driver not aware of ADS De-Activation.

No /Loss/too low - ADS Lateral Control													
Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severity Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	Driver not in control loop when ADS is Active , Loss of lateral control results in path deviation resulting in collision with adjacent lane cars or static objects outside the lane.
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	Due to collision delta speed (<10 kmph) ,No injuries in Highway scenario	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	Not Safety Relevant	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Obstruction in Lane	E2	Obstruction in highway lane - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)	Snow	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E2	Lo Mu Exposure - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S1	Due to collision delta speed (<10 kmph) ,light injuries for VRU	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Traffic Standstill	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	vehicle speed 0kmph.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	Not Safety Relevant	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Urban Driving condition with light traffic.	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S3	Due to collision with VRU with urban driving speed.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	

Incorrect ADS Lateral Control (too high)

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	Driver not in control loop when ADS is Active , too high lateral control results in EGO vehicle moving out of EGO lane.
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	Due to collision delta speed (<10 kmph) ,No injuries in Highway scenario.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	Not Safety Relevant	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Obstruction in Lane	E2	Obstruction in highway lane - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)	Snow	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E2	Lo Mu Exposure - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S1	Due to collision delta speed (<10 kmph) ,light injuries for VRU	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Traffic Standstill	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	vehicle speed 0kmph.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	Not Safety Relevant	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Urban Driving condition with light traffic.	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S3	Due to collision with VRU with urban driving speed.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	

Unintended ADS Lateral Control

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	Manual Mode	Any	E4	Manual driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	Lateral control from ADS when not in ADS Active mode. Driver Lateral Override	D	Unintended Lateral control by ADS in Manual driving mode , Driver loses lateral control resulting in collision.

No/Loss of ADS Longitudnal Control (Acceleration)

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C1	When EGO vehicle slows down, Rear car driver has control to overcome this scenario.	QM	EGO vehicle slows down and stops in case of Loss of longitudinal control.
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	Due to collision delta speed (<10 kmph) ,No injuries in Highway scenario	C1	When EGO vehicle slows down, Rear car driver has control to overcome this scenario.	QM	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Obstruction in Lane	E2	Obstruction in highway lane - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C1	When EGO vehicle slows down, Rear car driver has control to overcome this scenario.	QM	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)	Snow	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E2	Lo Mu Exposure - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C1	When EGO vehicle slows down, Rear car driver has control to overcome this scenario.	QM	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S1	Due to collision delta speed (<10 kmph) ,light injuries for VRU	C1	When EGO vehicle slows down, Rear car driver has control to overcome this scenario.	QM	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Traffic Standstill	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	vehicle speed 0kmph.	C1	When EGO vehicle slows down, Rear car driver has control to overcome this scenario.	QM	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Urban Driving condition with light traffic.	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	Vehicle stops in the event of loss of acceleration.	C1	When EGO vehicle slows down, Rear car driver has control to overcome this scenario.	QM	

Unintended ADS Longitudnal Control (Acceleration)

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	

Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S1	Due to collision delta speed (> 20 kmph) incase of unintended acceleration,Light injuries in Highway scenario	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	Unintended Acceleration when ADS is Active leading to Rear Ending lead vehicle on Highway and Collision with VRU in Urban.
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Obstruction in Lane	E2	Obstruction in highway lane - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
High+D71+A68:N74+A68:P74+A6+A71:M72	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)	Snow	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E2	Lo Mu Exposure - E2	S3	Due to collision delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S1	Due to collision delta speed (<10 kmph) , light injuries for VRU	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Traffic Standstill	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S2	Due to collision delta speed (>15 kmph) , incase of unintended acceleration with VRU	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	C	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Urban Driving condition with light traffic.	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S3	Due to collision with VRU with urban driving speed.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	

No/Loss of ADS Longitudnal Control (Braking)

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S3	No or insufficient braking resulting in collision with delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	No or insufficient braking from EGO vehicle resulting in collision with lead vehicle or with VRU in urban scenarios.
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	No or insufficient braking resulting in collision with delta speed (<10 kmph) ,No injuries in Highway scenario	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	Not Safety Relevant	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Obstruction in Lane	E2	Obstruction in highway lane - E2	S3	No or insufficient braking resulting in collision with delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)	Snow	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E2	Lo Mu Exposure - E2	S3	No or insufficient braking resulting in collision with delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S1	No or insufficient braking resulting in collision with delta speed (<10 kmph) , light injuries for VRU	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Traffic Standstill	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S1	No or insufficient braking resulting in collision with delta speed while vehicle roll over (<10 kmph) , light injuries for VRU	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	B	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Urban Driving condition with light traffic.	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S3	No or insufficient braking resulting in collision with VRU with urban driving speed.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated.	D	

Unintended ADS Longitudnal Control (Braking)

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S3	Unintended braking resulting in collision with delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C2	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Brake Light Activated. Rear Driver responds to EGO vehicle deceleration	C	

Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S0	Unintended braking resulting in collision with delta speed (<10 kmph) ,No injuries in Highway scenario	C2	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Brake Light Activated. Rear Driver responds to EGO vehicle deceleration	Not Safety Relevant	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Obstruction in Lane	E2	Obstruction in highway lane - E2	S3	Unintended braking resulting in collision with delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C2	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Brake Light Activated. Rear Driver responds to EGO vehicle deceleration	B	
Highway (max- 130kmph)	Highway with several lanes	Low Mu (<0.4)	Snow	ADS Active	No Traffic - Free Drive	E2	Lo Mu Exposure - E2	S3	Unintended braking resulting in collision with delta speed (> 60 Kph) , a S3 level can be expected.	C3	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Unintended braking cause driver to lose control of the vehicle.	B	Unintended braking from EGO vehicle resulting in collision with rear vehicle on highway.
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Slow movinf traffic < 10kmph	E4	ADS Driving exposure- E4	S1	Unintended braking resulting in collision with delta speed (<10 kmph) , light injuries for VRU	C1	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Brake Light Activated. Rear Driver responds to EGO vehicle deceleration	QM	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Traffic Standstill	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S1	Unintended braking resulting in collision with delta speed while vehicle roll over (<10 kmph) , light injuries for VRU	C1	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Brake Light Activated. Rear Driver responds to EGO vehicle deceleration	QM	
Urban roads (max- 50kmph)	Two way driving non divided with VRU's	Normal road condition (Mu > 0.8)	Normal condition	ADS Active	Urban Driving condition with light traffic.	E4	ADS Driving exposure in traffic scenario- E4	S1	Unintended braking resulting in collision with VRU with urban driving speed.	C1	Ego Driver not in control loop when ADS is activated. Brake Light Activated. Rear Driver responds to EGO vehicle deceleration	QM	

No ADS Take Over Request													
Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	ADS is activated. Driver not aware of ADS De-activated when no Take over request is issued.	D	No ADS Take over request is issued and ADS is de-activated , The Ego is not in control.

Unintended ADS Take Over Request													
Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C0	ADS is activated. Issues unintended Take over reqest. Driver annoyance.	QM	If no driver take over , vehicle performs MRM.

Incorrect ADS Take Over Request

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	Control not given back to the driver when requested	D	Driver not able to take back control of the ego vehicle.

No ADS Minium Risk Manuver

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	No Driver take over. Driver not in control.	D	ADS shall ensure safe stop in case of no driver take over.

Unintended ADS Minium Risk Manuver

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S2	Collision with delta speed < 60kmph on highway and < 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C0	ADS System making safe stop when not intended , Driver can override to take back control. Or Ego performs a safe stop	QM	Driver not able to take back control of the ego vehicle.

No ADS Status reported to driver

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	Driver not aware of current ADS State when loss of ADS status occurs.	D	Loss of ADS Status on a active hands free drive is safety critical , driver shall always be aware and notified of the correct and ADS State

Incorrect ADS Status reported to driver

Road type	Road layout	Surface Condition	Weather Conditions	Item Usage	Traffic Condition	Exposure	Exposure Comment	Severity	Severit Comment	Controlability	Controlability Comment	ASIL Rating	Comment
Any	Any	Any	Any	ADS Active	Any	E4	ADS Driving - E4	S3	Collision with delta speed > 60kmph on highway and > 30kmph with VRU in urban scenario	C3	Driver not aware of current ADS State	D	Driver performs hands off after ADS Status is confirmed. Correct ADS state information is critical for transition from Manual drive to hands free driving.

Safety Goal	ASIL	Responsible Functions
Ensure ADS status is correctly reported to the driver	D	ADS Status (Active/Inactive)
Prevent control not given back to the driver when requested	D	ADS Take Over Request
Prevent ADS use outside of ODD	D	ADS Activation / De-ADS Activation
Prevent insufficient/ unintended steering	D	ADS Lateral Control
Prevent unintended braking on system limit.	C	ADS Longitudnal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
Prevent loss or insufficient braking.	D	ADS Longitudnal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
Prevent unintended acceleration.	D	ADS Longitudnal Control (Acceleration & Braking)
Always activate brake lights when brakes are activated.	C	- General Body domain
Ensure safe stop in case of no driver take over	D	ADS Minimum Risk Maneuver

	Hazards
H1	Collision with stationary obstacle out of lane
H2	Collision with vulnerable road user
H3	Longitudinal collision with adjacent lanes objects
H4	Longitudinal collision with following vehicle
H5	Longitudinal collision with leading vehicle
H6	Reduced controllability of the vehicle by the driver
H7	Side collision with adjacent lanes objects
H8	Side collision with motorcycle
H9	ADS not able to cope with environment around

ASIL Determination Table				
Severity Class	Probability Class	Controllability Class		
		C1	C2	C3
S1	E1	QM	QM	QM
	E2	QM	QM	QM
	E3	QM	QM	A
	E4	QM	A	B
S2	E1	QM	QM	QM
	E2	QM	QM	A
	E3	QM	A	B
	E4	A	B	C
S3	E1	QM	QM	A
	E2	QM	A	B
	E3	A	B	C
	E4	B	C	D

Severity Evaluation Table				
	S0	S1	S2	S3
Front/ Rear	0-4	4-20	20-40	40-60
Side	0-2	2-8	8-16	16-40
	No Injuries	Light & Moderate Injuries	Severe and Life-threatening Injuries, Survival Probable	Life Threatening Injuries (Survival Uncertain), Fatal Injuries

CONTROLLABILITY RANKING				
Class	C0	C1	C2	C3
ISO 26262 Reference	Controllable in general	Simply controllable	Normally controllable	Difficult to control or uncontrollable
Reference Description	Full ability to maintain intended driving path	99% or more of all drivers or other traffic participants are usually able to avoid a specified harm - Ability to brake & steer to slow or stop vehicle	90% or more of all drivers or other traffic participants are usually able to avoid a specified harm	Less than 90% of all drivers or other traffic participants are usually able, or barely able, to avoid a specified harm

EXPOSURE RANKING					
Class	E0	E1	E2	E3	E4
ISO 26262 Reference	Incredible	Very low probability	Low probability	Medium probability	High probability
Reference Description	Not Specified	Situations that occur less often than once a year for the majority of drivers	< 1% of average operating time or situations that occur a few times a year for the great majority of drivers	1% - 10% of average operating time or situations that occur once a month or more often for an average driver	> 10% of average operating time or situations that occur during almost every drive cycle on average

Annex 4: STPA Step 4

UCA No.	UCA	Link to Hazards	What the Process Model Believes	Process Model Believes because	Causal Factor	CF Type	Requirement to Prevent the CF	Requirement to Detect the CF
UCA-6.1.1	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest during Night time when the CAV is operating on a motorway /jammed highway ramp/dense urban road,ADS is enabled,weather conditions are adverse (rain/snow/fog/ice on road) and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle/VRU in its path.	H-1,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided ADSBrakeRequest	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to provide brake request	The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
					AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was not sent out. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
					ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued
					The brake request calculated by the AutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the empty/faulty brake request from the Driver(unintended output) and hence incorrect/empty BrakeRequest(0Nm) is sent.	Conflicted Control	There shall be a mechanism to prevent/block unintentional inputs from the Driver	The Driver shall be made aware of potentially unintentional inputs.
					ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request	Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
					Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
					The control algorithm that determines when to send ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSBrakeRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
					Due to performance limitations of Sensors(owing to adverse weather and time of day), incorrect feedback signals(GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were sent.	PerformanceLimitations	The accuracy and performance of the Sensors shall not be inhibited by adverse weather conditions, poor visibility or occlusions.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the reduction in accuracy or performance of the Sensors and notify the Driver about this.
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request	Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued			
		Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors			

			AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
				<p>Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p>	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
				<p>Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Communication Error</p>	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
				<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
				<p>V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p>	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
				<p>Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Communication Error</p>	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
				<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to provide brake request	<p>The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect</p> <p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p>	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
				<p>AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was not sent out. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i></p> <p>Malfunctioning Controller</p>	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				<p>ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.</p> <p>Communication Error</p>	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
				<p>ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.</p> <p>Malfunctioning Actuator</p>	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued
				<p>The brake request calculated by theAutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the empty/faulty brake request from the Driver(unintended output) and hence incorrect/empty BrakeRequest(0Nm) is sent.</p> <p>Conflicted Control</p>	There shall be a mechanism to prevent/block unintentional inputs from the Driver	The Driver shall be made aware of potentially unintentional inputs.
			AutonomousDriveController	<p>ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.
				<p>Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p>	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued

UCA-6.1.2	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV is approaching a roundabout, there are no lead vehicles and there are vehicles approaching from the right.	H-2,4	believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
			AutonomousDriveController believes that there is no need to provide ADSBrakeRequest	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request	The control algorithm that determines when to send ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSBrakeRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to determine when ADSBrakeRequest must be issued, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)	
				Due to occlusions (tall grass or other obstructions) inaccurate feedback signals were sent from the Sensors	Performance Limitations	The accuracy and performance of the Sensors shall not be inhibited by adverse weather conditions, poor visibility, occlusions, etc.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the reduction in accuracy or performance of the Sensors and notify the Driver about this.	
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued	
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no vehicles approaching from the right.	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
			Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.		Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued	
			Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.		Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps	
			The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.		Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.	
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).	
				V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued	
				Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X	
The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.		If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.				
		The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.			

UCA-6.1.3	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV is operating on a motorway /highway/dense urban road, there is a malfunction/reduction of accuracy of the Perception&Localization, and	H-1,3	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to provide brake request	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was not sent out. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver				
				ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators				
				ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued				
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.			
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued			
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators			
				AutonomousDriveController believes that there is no need to provide ADSBrakeRequest	Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.			
					AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSBrakeRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.			
				AutonomousDriveController believes that there is no malfunction or reduction of accuracy of the Perception or Localization	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Self-Assessment to determine the status of Perception and Localisation.	H-1,3	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request	The SelfAssessmentStatus feedback issued by Self-Assessment is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The SelfAssessmentStatus shall reflect the actual status of the self assessment of the ADS system	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SelfAssessmentStatus and appropriate notifications issued
								The PerceptionReliabilityScore feedback issued by Self-Assessment is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	PerceptionReliabilityScore shall accurately indicate how reliable the perception system is.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated PerceptionReliabilityScore and appropriate notifications issued
Correct feedback signals were issued by Self-Assessment, but due to communication errors between Self-Assessment and AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signals were incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Self-Assessment shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Self-Assessment								
SelfAssessmentStatus feedback was correctly received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing SelfAssessmentStatus adequately to determine the status of Perception and Localisation	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process SelfAssessmentStatus, it shall notify the Driver.								
PerceptionReliabilityScore feedback was correctly received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing PerceptionReliabilityScore adequately to determine how reliable the perception system is	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process PerceptionReliabilityScore, it shall notify the Driver.								
The ObjectDetectionCheck feedback from Perception&Localization is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The ObjectDetectionCheck shall indicate accurately how well(range) objects can be detected,classified and tracked.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated ObjectDetectionCheck								
The LocalizationCheck feedback from Perception&Localization is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The LocalizationCheck shall indicate how accurately vehicle position can be localised	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated LocalizationCheck								
The ObjectTrackingCheck feedback from Perception&Localization is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The ObjectTrackingCheck shall indicate accurately how well(range) objects can be detected and tracked.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated ObjectTrackingCheck								
	The SensorVisibility feedback from Sensors is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The SensorVisibility shall provide an estimate of sensor effective visibility	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SensorVisibility							

the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle/VRU in its path.			The SensorObstruction feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The SensorObstruction shall provide an estimate of amount of sensor obstruction	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SensorObstruction		
			Self-Assessment correctly received all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck,LocalizationCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) , but incorrectly processed them.	Flawed Control Algorithm	Self assessment shall process all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck,LocalizationCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) to determine how reliable the perception and localisation systems are	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck,LocalizationCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) to generate a reliability score, it shall notify the Driver.		
			Self-Assessment correctly received all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) but was unable to process them correctly due to its malfunctions.	Malfunctioning Sensor	Self-Assessment shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of Self-Assessment and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver		
	AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV		The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)	
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued	
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.	
		AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position			The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
					Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
		AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV			The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.					Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued	
Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.					Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X	
The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.					Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.	
			The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.		

UCA-6.1.4	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, there is a reduction in accuracy of perception and localization and the CAV is approaching a slow speed zone(eg. due to road works or	H-3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to provide brake request	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was not sent out. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver		
				ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators		
				ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued		
				The brake request calculated by theAutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the empty/faulty brake request from the Driver(unintended output) and hence incorrect/empty BrakeRequest(0Nm) is sent.	Conflicted Control	There shall be a mechanism to prevent/block unintentional inputs from the Driver	The Driver shall be made aware of potentially unintentional inputs.		
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.	
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued	
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
					Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes that there is no need to provide ADSBrakeRequest	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request	The control algorithm that determines when to send ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSBrakeRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController does not believe that it is approaching a slow speed zone.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects (such as speed limit signs)around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
						Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
						Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
						The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the speed limits for the roads/zones.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).						
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued					
	Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps					

road traffic accidents with the presence of emergency vehicles).	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.	
		The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).	
		V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued	
		Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X	
		The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.	
	AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no accuracy issues with perception and localisation	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Self-Assessment to determine the accuracy of perception and localization	The SelfAssessmentStatus feedback from Self-Assessment was incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The SelfAssessmentStatus shall reflect the actual status of the self assessment of the ADS system	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SelfAssessmentStatus and appropriate notifications issued
			The PerceptionReliabilityScore feedback from Self-Assessment was incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	PerceptionReliabilityScore shall accurately indicate how reliable the perception system is.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated PerceptionReliabilityScore and appropriate notifications issued
			Correct feedback signals were issued, but due to a communication error between Self-Assessment and Autonomous Drive Controller, the feedback signals were not correctly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Self-Assessment shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Self-Assessment
			SelfAssessmentStatus feedback was correctly received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing SelfAssessmentStatus adequately to determine the status of Perception and Localisation	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process SelfAssessmentStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
			PerceptionReliabilityScore feedback was correctly received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing PerceptionReliabilityScore adequately to determine how reliable the perception system is	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process PerceptionReliabilityScore, it shall notify the Driver.
			The ObjectDetectionCheck feedback from Perception&Localization is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The ObjectDetectionCheck shall indicate accurately how well(range) objects can be detected,classified and tracked.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated ObjectDetectionCheck
			The ObjectTrackingCheck feedback from Perception&Localization is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The ObjectTrackingCheck shall indicate accurately how well(range) objects can be detected and tracked.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated ObjectTrackingCheck
			The SensorVisibility feedback from Sensors is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The SensorVisibility shall provide an estimate of sensor effective visibility	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SensorVisibility
			The SensorObstruction feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The SensorObstruction shall provide an estimate of amount of sensor obstruction	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SensorObstruction
AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no accuracy issues with perception and localisation	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Self-Assessment to determine the accuracy of perception and localization	Self-Assessment correctly received all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck), but incorrectly processed them.	Flawed Control Algorithm	Self assessment shall process all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck,LocalizationCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) to determine how reliable the perception and localisation systems are	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck,LocalizationCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) to generate a reliability score, it shall notify the Driver.	
		Self-Assessment correctly received all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) but was unable to process them correctly due to its malfunctions.	Malfunctioning Sensor	Self-Assessment shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of Self-Assessment and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver	
		The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.	

UCA-6.1.5	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, there are obstacles around the CAV, the Driver is not available/attentive and there is no response to the takeover request issued upon exit of ODD.	H-5,2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to provide brake request	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was not sent out. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver	
				ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				ADSBrakeRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued	
				ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.	
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued	
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request when the CAV exits its ODD	The control algorithm that determines when to send ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSBrakeRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)
			Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.		Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued	
			Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.		Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors	
			The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.		Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.	
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).				
	Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued				
	Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps				
	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.				

			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
				V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
				Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
				The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that the Driver is attentive/available and has taken over control of the DDT.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the DriverOverrideStatus feedback from the VehicleMotionController to determine whether the Driver was controlling the CAV.	The DriverOverrideStatus feedback from VehicleMotionController was incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverOverrideStatus shall indicate correctly whether the Driver has overridden the ADS requests or not	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous DriverOverrideStatus
				Correct DriverOverrideStatus feedback signal was issued, but due to a communication error between VehicleMotionController and Autonomous Drive Controller, the signal was not correctly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleMotionController
				DriverOverrideStatus feedback was correctly received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing DriverOverrideStatus to determine whether the Driver is in control of the DDT	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process DriverOverrideStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because there is no feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on the Driver presence or attentiveness.	A feedback signal on Driver Availability is missing in the design. Note : This would need to include a Driver availability recognition system including internal cameras to monitor driver attentiveness.	Missing Feedback	There shall be a feedback to inform the AutonomousDriveController whether the Driver is attentive and available to take over DDT.	AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify the driver availability status from other sources.
				A feedback signal on Driver seat belt status is missing in the design.	Missing Feedback	There shall be a feedback to inform the AutonomousDriveController of the Driver Seat belt status	AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify the driver Seat belt status from other sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide brake request.	The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was incorrectly sent. Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				ADSBrakeRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, incorrect BrakeRequest was received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
				ADSBrakeRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued
				VehicleMotionController received the correct brake request from AutonomousDriveController, but it was overwritten by the faulty/unintentional brake request from the Driver.	Conflicted Control	The Vehicle Motion Controller shall be able to identify false/unintended requests from the Driver and prioritise the requests from the AutonomousDriveController over these erroneous requests.	If the requests from the Autonomous Drive Controller have been overridden by the false/unintended inputs from the Driver,the Autonomous Drive Controller shall be notified about it.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that the brake request provided was correct.	AutonomousDriveController	ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued

UCA-6.2.1	AutonomousDriveController provides insufficient ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled , the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path and there is an imminent collision risk.	H-1,3	believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators					
				Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.					
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)					
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued				
									Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
									The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The classification of objects may be incorrect, for eg: a significant object may be classified as insignificant or the relative position and speed of dynamic obstacles/VRUs may be inaccurate.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) to detect , classify objects accurately and track them	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
									The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
									Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
									Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
									The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
									AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback
			V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued						
			Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X						
			The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The relative position and speed of dynamic obstacles/VRUs calculated by the AutonomousDriveController may be inaccurate.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.						
						The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.			

UCA-6.2.2	AutonomousDriveController provides insufficient ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled and the current speed of the CAV is too high to navigate around an approaching sharp bend (narrow curve radii).	H-2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that the brake request provided was correct.	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was incorrectly sent. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver	
				ADSBrakeRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, incorrect BrakeRequest was received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				ADSBrakeRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued	
				VehicleMotionController received the correct brake request from AutonomousDriveController, but it was overwritten by the faulty/unintentional brake request from the Driver.	Conflicted Control	The Vehicle Motion Controller shall be able to identify false/unintended requests from the Driver and prioritise the requests from the AutonomousDriveController over these erroneous requests.	If the requests from the Autonomous Drive Controller have been overridden by the false/unintended inputs from the Driver, the Autonomous Drive Controller shall be notified about it.	
				ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.	
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued	
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	The IMUData feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The IMUData feedback signal shall indicate accurate IMU data	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous IMUData
					The WheelSpeed feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelSpeed feedback signal shall indicate accurate wheel speed	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelSpeed
					Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were issued by Sensors, but due to a communication error between Sensors and Autonomous Drive Controller, the signals were not correctly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
					Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing IMUData & WheelSpeed to determine the actual vehicle speed	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process IMUData & WheelSpeed, it shall notify the Driver
					Sensors are malfunctioning, hence feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	Sensors shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback signal shall indicate accurate 6DOF position and orientation	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous 6DOFPosition&Orientation
The WheelRotations feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelRotations feedback signal shall indicate accurate value of wheel rotations	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelRotations					
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the road curvature	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).				
	Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued				
	Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps				

					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.			
UCA-6.2.3	AutonomousDriveController provides excessive ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, there are moving vehicles ahead of the CAV and other vehicles following closely behind. <i>Note: This may lead to a rear obstacle collision</i>	H-3	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide brake request.	AutonomousDriveController believes that the brake request provided was correct.	The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect,	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSBrakeRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSBrakeRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.			
					AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was incorrectly sent. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver			
					ADSBrakeRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, incorrect BrakeRequest was received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators			
					ADSBrakeRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveControleer to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued			
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.			
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued			
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators			
					Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.			
			AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no vehicles following closely behind	AutonomousDriveController provides excessive ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, there are moving vehicles ahead of the CAV and other vehicles following closely behind. <i>Note: This may lead to a rear obstacle collision</i>	H-3	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
								Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
								Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
								The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position				The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).		
						Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued		
						Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps		

					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV		The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
					V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The relative position and speed of dynamic obstacles/VRUs calculated by the AutonomousDriveController may be inaccurate.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide brake request.		The control algorithm that sends ADSBrakeRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSBrakeRequest must be issued	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications
					AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSBrakeRequest was fault-issued. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					ADSBrakeRequest was not sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), BrakeRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued
					ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSBrakeStatus signals.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation		Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSBrakeStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
					Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSBrakeStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV		Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
					Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
UCA-6.3.1			AutonomousDriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, there are vehicles following the CAV closely behind and there are no obstacles ahead. Note: This may lead to a rear	H-3				

obstacle collision.	AutonomousDriveController believes that there are obstacles ahead of the CAV.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
			The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
			Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
			Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
		AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
			V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
			Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
			The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The relative position and speed of dynamic obstacles/VRUs calculated by the AutonomousDriveController may be inaccurate.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide ADSBrakeRequest	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is flawed.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue brake request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications
			The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that brake request is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the brake request exceeds a defined threshold value,appropriate notifications shall be issued
ADSBrakeRequest was issued at the right time, but due to a communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay		The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSBrakeRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued		
The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.	Actuator Degradation		The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.		
The ADSBrakeStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback		The ADSBrakeStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of brake implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSBrakeStatus.		
AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	BrakeStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSBrakeStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued		
	Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSBrakeStatus was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of BrakeStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.		

UCA-6.5.1	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, the CAV is operating on a motorway /jammed highway ramp/dense urban road, at Night, weather conditions are adverse(rain/snow/fog/ice on road) and there is a significant obstacle (eg: parked vehicle, decelerating lead vehicle, road works, blocked lane etc.)or a VRU in the CAV path.	H-1,3			AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSBrakeStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSBrakeStatus exceeds a defined threshold value,appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS is not enabled/Driver is in control of DDT	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to EnableAD to determine the ADS status.	The EnableAD command from HMI was delayed.	Delayed Control Input	The EnableAD command from HMI shall be received by the Autonomous Drive Controller within a specified duration once the Driver has requested for activation of ADS.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays in issuing EnableAD.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that time of day and weather conditions are favorable for operation of the ADS	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the time of day and weather conditions	The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature,Humidity,AmbientLighting) were inadequately updated.	Delayed Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of the weather conditions with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature,Humidity,AmbientLighting)
					The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature,Humidity,AmbientLighting)were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature,Humidity,AmbientLighting) due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
					The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature,Humidity, Ambient lighting)were received on time on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, Ambient lighting) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature,Humidity, Ambient lighting) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no obstacles or VRUs in the CAV path	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) were inadequately updated. <i>Note:This could be due to performance limitations owing to adverse weather and time of day</i>	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) due to performance limitations owing to adverse weather and time of day
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) due to communication delays
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,Rawlmage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage)
					The feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage) due to communication delays
					The feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage)was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (Maplimage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) due to communication delays

				objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
UCA-6.5.2	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled , the CAV is approaching a roundabout, there are no lead vehicles and there are vehicles approaching from the right	H-2,3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided ADSBrakeRequest at the right time	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide ADSBrakeRequest	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is flawed.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue brake request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications
					The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that brake request is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the brake request exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
					ADSBrakeRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSBrakeRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
					The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of brake implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSBrakeStatus.
					BrakeStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSBrakeStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSBrakeStatus was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of BrakeStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
					AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSBrakeStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSBrakeStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS is not enabled/Driver is in control of DDT	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to EnableAD to determine the ADS status.	The EnableAD command from HMI was delayed.	Delayed Control Input	The EnableAD command from HMI shall be received by the Autonomous Drive Controller within a specified duration once the Driver has requested for activation of ADS.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays in issuing EnableAD.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays
The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV.			If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued			
AutonomousDriveController believes	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback		The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)			

			that there are no vehicles approaching from the right/they are far away	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) due to communication delays
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide ADSBrakeRequest	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is flawed.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue brake request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications
					The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that brake request is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the brake request exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
					ADSBrakeRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSBrakeRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
				AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided ADSBrakeRequest at the right time	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	There was a delay in the update of ADSBrakeStatus feedback.	Delayed Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of brake implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSBrakeStatus.
					BrakeStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSBrakeStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
					Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSBrakeStatus was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of BrakeStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
					AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSBrakeStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSBrakeStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
UCA-6.5.3	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled and the CAV is approaching a red traffic light.	H-3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS is not enabled/Driver is in control of DDT	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to EnableAD to determine the ADS status.	The EnableAD command from HMI was delayed.	Delayed Control Input	The EnableAD command from HMI shall be received by the Autonomous Drive Controller within a specified duration once the Driver has requested for activation of ADS.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays in issuing EnableAD.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.

			AutonomousDriveController believes that the traffic light is far ahead or not showing red	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data. <i>Note: The distance and color of traffic lights must be processed accurately and in a timely manner</i></p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the distance and color of traffic lights.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays</p> <p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.</p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays</p> <p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
UCA-6.5.4	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled and the CAV is approaching a sharp turn/bend/curve.	H-2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided ADSBrakeRequest at the right time	<p>The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is flawed.</p> <p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p> <p>The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.</p> <p>Processing Delay</p> <p>ADSBrakeRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.</p> <p>Actuator Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue brake request at the right time and for the required duration.</p> <p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that brake request is issued at the right time</p> <p>The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications</p> <p>If the processing time for the calculation of the brake request exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSBrakeRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	<p>There was a delay in the update of ADSBrakeStatus feedback.</p> <p>Delayed Feedback</p> <p>BrakeStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus was not received on time.</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSBrakeStatus was not updated on time.</p> <p>Sensor Degradation</p> <p>AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSBrakeStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.</p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The ADSBrakeStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of brake implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is updated on time.</p> <p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus within a specified duration of time.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSBrakeStatus.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSBrakeStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of BrakeStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.</p> <p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSBrakeStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS is not enabled/Driver is in	<p>The EnableAD command from HMI was delayed.</p> <p>Delayed Control Input</p>	<p>The EnableAD command from HMI shall be received by the Autonomous Drive Controller within a specified duration once the Driver has requested for activation of ADS.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delays in issuing EnableAD.</p>

		control of DDT	AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that the sharp turn/bend/curve is still further ahead	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
		The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays		Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays	
		The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.		Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
		AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided ADSBrakeRequest at the right time	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide ADSBrakeRequest	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is flawed. <i>Note: The control algorithm must cater for steady braking in the ego lane in a timely manner when there is no response to take over request issued upon exit of ODD</i>	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue brake request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications
				The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSBrakeRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that brake request is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the brake request exceeds a defined threshold value,appropriate notifications shall be issued
				ADSBrakeRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSBrakeRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
				The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	There was a delay in the update of ADSBrakeStatus feedback.	Delayed Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of brake implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSBrakeStatus.
				BrakeStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSBrakeStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSBrakeStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSBrakeStatus was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of BrakeStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
				AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSBrakeStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSBrakeStatus exceeds a defined threshold value,appropriate notifications shall be issued

UCA-6.5.5	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, there are obstacles around the CAV, and there is no response to the takeover request issued upon exit of ODD.	H-5,2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that the obstacles are still further ahead	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)		
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays		
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued		
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)		
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays		
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued		
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)		
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) due to communication delays		
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) within a specified duration of time to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued		
				AutonomousDriveController believes that the Driver has responded to the take-over request in a timely manner	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller	AutonomousDriveController believes that the Driver has responded to the take-over request in a timely manner	The DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverOverrideStatus shall be updated on time to indicate correctly whether the Driver has overridden the ADS requests or not	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrectly updated DriverOverrideStatus
							The DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Motion Controller shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated DriverOverrideStatus due to communication delays
							The DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing DriverOverrideStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the DriverOverrideStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
There was a delay in the issue of TakeOverRequest	Delayed Feedback	The Autonomous Drive Controller shall issue TakeOverRequest in a timely manner when required.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed TakeOverRequest							
TakeOverRequest was issued on time, but due to sensor (HMI)degradation, the Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings were not issued on time	Sensor Degradation	The HMI shall be well maintained, ensuring that Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings are issued/updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings due to HMI degradation and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.							
TakeOverRequest was issued on time, but due to sensor (HMI)degradation, DisplayedADStatus was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The HMI shall be well maintained, ensuring that DisplayedADStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of DisplayedADStatus due to HMI degradation and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.							

				TakeOverRequest was issued on time but due to delay in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and the HMI, Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings were not issued on time	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings due to communication delays
				TakeOverRequest was issued on time but due to delay in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and the HMI, DisplayedADStatus was not updated on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated DisplayedADStatus due to communication delays
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
UCA-6.7.1	AutonomousDriveController stops providing ADSBrakeRequest too soon during the Night time when the CAV is operating on a motorway /highway/dense urban road, ADS is enabled, weather conditions are adverse(rain/snow/fog/ice on the road), the CAV is approaching a significant	H-1,2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide brake request.	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the brake request anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be able to continuously process brake request when required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to control algorithm degradation
				AutonomousDriveController is degraded and hence ADSBrakeRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide brake request continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController
				ADSBrakeRequest was being issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators
				ADSBrakeRequest was still being issued, but due to actuator degradations, the BrakeRequest was not implemented anymore.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously implemented upon request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to degradation of the actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators
			AutonomousDriveController believes that it is continuing to provide brake request.	The ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the brake implementation status.	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSBrakeStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of brake request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect ADSBrakeStatus.
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, the feedback was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSBrakeStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, the ADSBrakeStatus feedback was not correctly sensed anymore.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the ADSBrakeStatus feedback is continuously received.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSBrakeStatus due to sensor degradations
				AutonomousDriveController receives correct ADSBrakeStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process ADSBrakeStatus continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process ADSBrakeStatus .
			AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS has been disabled/ADS has been disabled/Driver has taken over control of the DDT.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverOverrideStatus shall be updated on time to indicate correctly whether the Driver has overridden the ADS requests or not	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrectly updated DriverOverrideStatus
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)shall be updated correctly	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
				Correct feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were issued by Sensors, but due to degradation in the communication channel between Sensors and AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signals were not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors

<p>approaching a dangerous obstacle/VRU in its path and an imminent collision risk prevails.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has already evaded the obstacle/VRU and there is no more collision risk</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController receives correct feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signals anymore.</p>	<p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) continuously</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc).</p>
		<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated correctly</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)</p>
		<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between Maps and AutonomousDriveController</p>	<p>Communication Degradation</p>	<p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is continuously propagated.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps.</p>
		<p>AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.</p>	<p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)continuously</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)</p>
		<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated correctly</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)</p>
		<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between V2X and AutonomousDriveController</p>	<p>Communication Degradation</p>	<p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is continuously propagated.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X.</p>
	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.</p>	<p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)continuously</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)</p>
		<p>The feedback signal from the Sensors (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting) were inadequately updated.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting) shall be updated correctly</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting)</p>
		<p>The feedback signal from the Sensors (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting)were not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between Sensors and AutonomousDriveController</p>	<p>Communication Degradation</p>	<p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signals (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting) are continuously propagated.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signals (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting)continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors</p>
		<p>AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signals anymore.</p>	<p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signals (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting) continuously</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signals (Temperature,Humidity, AmbientLighting)</p>
	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that weather conditions are favourable/have improved</p>	<p>There is no feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on road surface conditions.</p>	<p>Missing Feedback</p>	<p>There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on road surface conditions.</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify road surface conditions from other available sources.</p>
		<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because there is no specific feedback included on road surface conditions</p>	<p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be able to continuously process brake request when required.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to control algorithm degradation</p>
<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it is continuing to provide brake request.</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the brake request anymore.</p>	<p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be able to continuously process brake request when required.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to control algorithm degradation</p>	
	<p>AutonomousDriveController is degraded and hence ADSBrakeRequest is not issued anymore.</p>	<p>Controller Degradations</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously issued when needed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide brake request continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController</p>	
	<p>ADSBrakeRequest was being issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received anymore.</p>	<p>Communication Degradation</p>	<p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously propagated.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators</p>	
	<p>ADSBrakeRequest was still being issued, but due to actuator degradations, the BrakeRequest was not implemented anymore.</p>	<p>Actuator Degradation</p>	<p>The actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously implemented upon request.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to degradation of the actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators</p>	
<p>The ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the brake implementation status.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The ADSBrakeStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of brake request.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect ADSBrakeStatus.</p>		

UCA-6.7.2	AutonomousDriveController stops providing ADSBrakeRequest too soon when ADS is enabled and the current vehicle speed is still high for the situation (Eg: maneuvering a sharp bend/turn, approaching a slow speed zone with roadworks, decelerating lead vehicle, etc.)	H-2,3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of brake request implementation.	Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, the feedback was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSBrakeStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators	
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, the ADSBrakeStatus feedback was not correctly sensed anymore.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the ADSBrakeStatus feedback is continuously received.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSBrakeStatus due to sensor degradations	
				AutonomousDriveController receives correct ADSBrakeStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process ADSBrakeStatus continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process ADSBrakeStatus .	
			AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS has been disabled/Driver has taken over control of the DDT.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller	The DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverOverrideStatus shall be updated on time to indicate correctly whether the Driver has overridden the ADS requests or not	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrectly updated DriverOverrideStatus
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that the current speed of the CAV is appropriate for the situation.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine vehicle speed	The IMUData feedback from Sensors is not updated properly.	Inadequate Feedback	The IMUData feedback signal shall indicate accurate IMU data	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous IMUData
					The WheelSpeed feedback from Sensors is not updated properly.	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelSpeed feedback signal shall indicate accurate wheel speed	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelSpeed
					Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were issued by Sensors, but due to a degradation in the communication channel between Sensors and Autonomous Drive Controller, the signals were not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) are continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
					Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were received but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback signals anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed)
					The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback from Vehicle Actuators is not updated properly.	Inadequate Feedback	The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback signal shall indicate accurate 6DOF position and orientation	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous 6DOFPosition&Orientation
					The WheelRotations feedback from Vehicle Actuators is not updated properly.	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelRotations feedback signal shall indicate accurate value of wheel rotations	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelRotations
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the road curvature	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated correctly	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between Maps and AutonomousDriveController	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps.
					AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(slow speed zone, roadworks, decelerating lead vehicle etc.)	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated correctly	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)
The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between V2X and AutonomousDriveController	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is continuously propagated.			There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X.			
AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) continuously			There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)			

				<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)shall be updated correctly</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(slow speed zone, roadworks, decelerating lead vehicle etc.)</p>	<p>Correct feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were issued by Sensors, but due to degradation in the communication channel between Sensors and AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signals were not received anymore.</p> <p>Communication Degradation</p>	<p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are continuously propagated.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors</p>
				<p>AutonomousDriveController receives correct feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signals anymore.</p> <p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) continuously</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc).</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(slow speed zone, roadworks, decelerating lead vehicle etc.)</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the brake request anymore.</p> <p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be able to continuously process brake request when required.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to control algorithm degradation</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController is degraded and hence ADSBrakeRequest is not issued anymore.</p> <p>Controller Degradations</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously issued when needed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide brake request continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController</p>	
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide brake request.</p>	<p>ADSBrakeRequest was being issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, BrakeRequest was not received anymore.</p> <p>Communication Degradation</p>	<p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously propagated.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it is continuing to provide brake request.</p>	<p>ADSBrakeRequest was still being issued, but due to actuator degradations, the BrakeRequest was not implemented anymore.</p> <p>Actuator Degradation</p>	<p>The actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously implemented upon request.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to degradation of the actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of brake request implementation.</p>	<p>The ADSBrakeStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the brake implementation status.</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The ADSBrakeStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of brake request.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect ADSBrakeStatus.</p>
				<p>Correct ADSBrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, the feedback was not received anymore.</p> <p>Communication Degradation</p>	<p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeStatus is continuously propagated.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSBrakeStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators</p>
				<p>Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, the ADSBrakeStatus feedback was not correctly sensed anymore.</p> <p>Sensor Degradation</p>	<p>The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the ADSBrakeStatus feedback is continuously received.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSBrakeStatus due to sensor degradations</p>
				<p>AutonomousDriveController receives correct ADSBrakeStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.</p> <p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process ADSBrakeStatus continuously</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process ADSBrakeStatus .</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS has been disabled/Driver has taken over control of the DDT.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller</p> <p>The DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller was inadequately updated.</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The DriverOverrideStatus shall be updated on time to indicate correctly whether the Driver has overridden the ADS requests or not</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrectly updated DriverOverrideStatus</p>
				<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV</p> <p>The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing</p> <p>Missing Feedback</p>	<p>There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that a safe stopping location has been reached.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the controller logic to determine that a safe stopping location had been reached</p> <p>The control algorithm that determines whether a safe stopping location has been reached is degraded</p> <p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to determine whether a safe stopping location has been reached or not.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to determine whether a safe stopping location has been reached or not.</p>
				<p>Feedback must be included in the design to inform the AutonomousDriveController of the criteria for a safe stopping location.</p> <p>Missing Feedback</p>	<p>There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on the criteria for a safe stopping location</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify a safe stopping location from other available sources.</p>
UCA-6.7.3	AutonomousDriveController stops providing ADSBrakeRequest too soon when ADS is in a degraded mode performing a MRM, there are significant	H-1,2,3				

obstacles/VRUs in the path of the CAV, and a safe stopping location has not been reached.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated correctly	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)	
		The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between Maps and AutonomousDriveController	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps.	
		AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)	
		The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated correctly	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)	
		The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between V2X and AutonomousDriveController	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X.	
		AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)	
	AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no longer any significant obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path/lane of travel	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) shall be updated correctly to indicate the presence/position of objects around the CAV and lane markings	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)
			Correct feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were issued by Sensors, but due to degradation in the communication channel between Sensors and AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signals were not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
			AutonomousDriveController receives correct feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signals anymore. <i>Note: The Autonomous Drive Controller must be able to process these feedback signals in a timely manner to determine the lane markings/lane boundaries</i>	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)
	AutonomousDriveController believes that it is no longer in a degraded mode performing MRM	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it followed the control algorithm to determine whether ADS is in a degraded mode or not	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController that determines when the ADS is in a degraded mode is inadequate/degraded <i>Note: The requirements on when the ADS must enter degraded mode and what actions must be taken may be inadequate</i>	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to determine when the ADS must switch to a degraded mode and what actions must be taken thereafter.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to determine when the ADS must switch to a degraded mode and what actions must be taken thereafter.
			The control algorithm within AutonomousDriveController that sends steering request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSSteerRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide steering request	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide steering request	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSSteerRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of the AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
ADSSteerRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between the Drive Control Unit and the Vehicle Actuators, Steer Request was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.			Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
ADSSteerRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), SteerRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.			Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator (VehicleMotionController) and appropriate notifications issued	

UCA-7.1.1	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, there is a significant obstacle(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works or special vehicles) or a suddenly appearing VRU in the lane of the CAV and adjacent lanes are available /free of obstacles	H-1,3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided Steer Request	The steer request calculated by the AutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the empty/faulty steer request from the Driver(unintended output) and hence empty SteerRequest is sent.	Conflicted Control	There shall be a mechanism to prevent/block unintentional inputs from the Driver	The Driver shall be made aware of potentially unintentional inputs.			
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation	ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSSteerStatus signals.			
				Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSSteerStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications issued			
				Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators			
				Correct ADSSteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSSteerStatus, it shall notify the Driver.			
			AutonomousDriveController believes that it should not send steering request	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it has correctly followed the control algorithm not to send steering request.	The specified control algorithm for sending steering request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSSteerRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.		
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) to determine the presence/relative position of objects around the CAV, their size and lane markings	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)		
					Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued		
					Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors		
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.		
					AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	AutonomousDriveController believes that the CAV is not approaching an object of significant size in its path	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
							Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
							Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
							The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the V2X (V2XObjectData).		
V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent			There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued					
Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.			There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X					

					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the sensor fusion algorithm to determine whether the object is significant or not	The sensor fusion algorithm that determines whether an object is significant or not is inadequate/incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The sensor fusion algorithm shall be able to accurately determine whether an object is significant or not	There shall be a mechanism to detect the inability of the AutonomousDriveController to accurately determine whether an object is significant or not	
UCA-7.1.2	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve and is too close to the border.	H-2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided Steer Request	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide steering request	The control algorithm within AutonomousDriveController that sends steering request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSSteerRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.	
					AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSSteerRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of the AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver	
					ADSSteerRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between the Drive Control Unit and the Vehicle Actuators, Steer Request was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
					ADSSteerRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), SteerRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation	The steer request calculated by the AutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the empty/faulty steer request from the Driver (unintended output) and hence empty SteerRequest is sent.	Conflicted Control	There shall be a mechanism to prevent/block unintentional inputs from the Driver	The Driver shall be made aware of potentially unintentional inputs.	
					ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSSteerStatus signals.	
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSSteerStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications issued	
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position and the road curvature	Correct ADSSteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSSteerStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
					AutonomousDriveController believes that because it has correctly followed the control algorithm not to send steering request.	The specified control algorithm for sending steering request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSSteerRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
					AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position and the road curvature	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect, ie it doesn't adequately represent the road curvature/layout.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall accurately represent the CAV position and road curvature/layout	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
						Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position and the road curvature	Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps					
	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position and road curvature/layout	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.					

			AutonomousDriveController believes that is not navigating a sharp turn/bend/curve and is not too close to the border.		The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) to determine the presence/relative position of objects around the CAV and lane markings/boundaries	Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
					Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
UCA-7.1.3	AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled and the CAV is merging onto the main road from a ramp.	H-2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided Steer Request	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide steering request	The control algorithm within AutonomousDriveController that sends steering request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSSteerRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
					AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSSteerRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of the AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					ADSSteerRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between the Drive Control Unit and the Vehicle Actuators, Steer Request was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
					ADSSteerRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), SteerRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued
					The steer request calculated by the AutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the empty/faulty steer request from the Driver(unintended output) and hence empty SteerRequest is sent.	Conflicted Control	There shall be a mechanism to prevent/block unintentional inputs from the Driver	The Driver shall be made aware of potentially unintentional inputs.
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation	ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSSteerStatus signals.
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSSteerStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications issued
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
					Correct ADSSteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSSteerStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
							AutonomousDriveController believes that it should not send steering request	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it has correctly followed the control algorithm not to send steering request.
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect, ie it does not adequately represent the forward road scene	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall accurately represent the CAV position and the road layout/forward road scene	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
					Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued

			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position and the road layout/forward road scene	Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
		AutonomousDriveController believes that it is navigating a straight path		The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position and the road layout/forward road scene	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
		AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) to determine the presence/relative position of objects around the CAV and lane markings/boundaries	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequatelyto determine the presence/relative position of objects around the CAV and lane markings/boundaries	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that the steer request provided was correct.	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide steer request.	The control algorithm that calculates steer request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSSteerRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSSteerRequest was incorrectly sent. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				ADSSteerRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, SteerRequest was incorrectly received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
				ADSSteerRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), SteerRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator (VehicleMotionController) and appropriate notifications issued
				The correct Steer request calculated by the AutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the faulty steer request from the Driver(unintended output) and hence incorrect Steer Request is sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Conflicted Control	The Vehicle Motion Controller shall be able to identify false/unintended requests from the Driver and prioritise the requests from the AutonomousDriveController over these erroneous requests.	If the requests from the Autonomous Drive Controller have been overridden by the false/unintended inputs from the Driver,the Autonomous Drive Controller shall be notified about it.
		AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation	ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSSteerStatus signals.
				Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSSteerStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications issued
				Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
				Correct ADSSteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSSteerStatus, it shall notify the Driver.

UCA-7.2.1	AutonomousDriveController provides incorrect ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, weather conditions are adverse (heavy rain/snow/fog/ice on the road), the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve and is too close to the border.	H-2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that the steering request provided is suitable for the weather conditions	The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) shall be updated accurately	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting)	
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, Ambient lighting) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued	
				The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) were not received/incorrectly received due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController,	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors	
				The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, Ambient lighting) were correctly received, but were misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, Ambient lighting) to determine the time of day, weather conditions and road conditions	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, Ambient lighting) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on the road surface conditions	Missing Feedback	There shall be a feedback to the AutonomousDriveController from Sensors on road surface conditions	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to determine the road surface conditions from some other sources.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because there is no feedback/input on the steering performance requirements in adverse weather conditions	Missing Feedback	There shall be a feedback to the AutonomousDriveController from the Manufacturer on steering performance in adverse weather conditions	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to gather inputs on steering performance in adverse weather conditions from some other sources.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position and the road curvature	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect, ie it doesn't adequately represent the road curvature/layout.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall accurately represent the the CAV position and the road curvature	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
					Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the the CAV position and the road curvature	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that the CAV is not too close to the border	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)
					Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
					Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. Note: The controller doesn't adequately process the input signals to determine the road curvature, layout, lane markings etc.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the determine the road curvature, layout, lane markings etc	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
Due to performance limitations of the Sensors (owing to adverse weather), the feedback signals from the Sensors (PointCloud, RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated	Performance Limitations(sensor)	The accuracy and performance of the Sensors shall not be inhibited by adverse weather conditions, poor visibility or occlusions.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the reduction in accuracy or performance of the Sensors and notifications issued to the Driver					
The control algorithm that calculates steer request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSSteerRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.					

UCA-7.2.2	AutonomousDriveController provides incorrect ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, there is a VRU(cyclist/horse-rider/mobility scooter user) in the lane of travel of the CAV and the CAV is performing an overtake maneuver.	H-2	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide steer request.	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSSteerRequest was incorrectly sent. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				ADSSteerRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, SteerRequest was incorrectly received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
				ADSSteerRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), SteerRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator (VehicleMotionController) and appropriate notifications issued
				The correct Steer request calculated by the AutonomousDriveController is overwritten by the faulty steer request from the Driver(unintended output) and hence incorrect Steer Request is sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Conflicted Control	The Vehicle Motion Controller shall be able to identify false/unintended requests from the Driver and prioritise the requests from the AutonomousDriveController over these erroneous requests.	If the requests from the Autonomous Drive Controller have been overridden by the false/unintended inputs from the Driver,the Autonomous Drive Controller shall be notified about it.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation	ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSSteerStatus signals.
				Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSSteerStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications issued
				Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
				Correct ADSSteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSSteerStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) to determine the presence/relative position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The distance to the objects and their relative position/speed are miscalculated based on the feedback signals from the sensors</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence/relative position and speed of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
AutonomousDriveController believes that the lateral distance to the VRU is sufficient for an overtake manoeuvre	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall accurately represent the the CAV position	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).			
	Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued			
	Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps			

					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV		The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
					V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. Note: The distance to the objects and their relative position/speed are miscalculated based on the feedback signals from V2X	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide steer request.		The control algorithm that calculates steer request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSSteerRequest when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
					AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSSteerRequest was incorrectly sent. Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					ADSSteerRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, SteerRequest was incorrectly received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communications channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
					ADSSteerRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), SteerRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator (VehicleMotionController) and appropriate notifications issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation		ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSSteerStatus signals.
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSSteerStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications issued
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
					Correct ADSSteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSSteerStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position		The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect, ie it doesn't adequately represent the road curvature/layout.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall accurately represent the the CAV position	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
					Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
UCA-7.2.3	AutonomousDriveController provides incorrect(excessive) ADSSteerRequest when ADS is enabled, lane markings are faded/absent and there are	H-2						

	<p>obstacles adjacent to the CAV.</p>		<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that the CAV is keeping to its lane</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) to determine the lane markings/boundaries</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.</p>	<p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position</p>	<p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no obstacles adjacent to the CAV</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV</p>	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. Note: The controller doesn't adequately process the input signals to determine the road layout and lane boundaries in the absence of lane markings.</p>	<p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the road layout and lane boundaries in the absence of lane markings.</p>	<p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no obstacles adjacent to the CAV</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide steer request.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.</p>	<p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p>	<p>The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSSteerRequest</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.</p>	<p>Communication Error</p>	<p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSSteerRequest</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. Note: The distance to the objects and their relative position/speed are miscalculated based on the feedback signals from V2X</p>	<p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the distance to the objects around CAV and their relative position/speed.</p>	<p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide steer request.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>The control algorithm that sends ADSSteerRequest is incorrect</p>	<p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSSteerRequest when required</p>	<p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSSteerRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide steer request.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSSteerRequest was fault-issued. Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</p>	<p>Malfunctioning Controller</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide steer request.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>ADSSteerRequest was not sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), SteerRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.</p>	<p>Malfunctioning Actuator</p>	<p>Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator (VehicleMotionController) and appropriate notifications issued</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSSteerRequest</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The ADSSteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSSteerStatus signals.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSSteerRequest</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSSteerStatus is sent</p>	<p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p>	<p>Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications issued</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSSteerRequest</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation</p>	<p>Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus is incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.</p>	<p>Communication Error</p>	<p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators</p>

UCA-7.3.1	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSSteerRequest (lane change) when ADS is enabled, there is an insignificant(overdriveable) obstacle(eg:leaf, mud) in the CAV path and there are vehicles in adjacent lanes.	H-2	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV and their size	Correct ADSSteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSSteerStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)	
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued	
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The classification of objects(significant/insignificant) based on these input signals may be incorrect</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the the presence / position of objects around the CAV and their size	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall accurately represent the the CAV position	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
					Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV and their size	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
					V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
					The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The presence/position of objects and their classification may be inaccurate.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV and their size	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the sensor fusion algorithm to determine whether the object is significant or not	The sensor fusion algorithm that determines whether an object is significant or not is inadequate/incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The sensor fusion algorithm shall be able to accurately determine whether an object is significant or not	There shall be a mechanism to detect the inability of the AutonomousDriveController to accurately determine whether an object is significant or not
AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSSteerRequest is flawed. <i>Note: The control algorithm must cater for steady braking in the ego lane in a timely manner when there is no response to take over request issued upon exit of ODD</i>	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue steer request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications				
	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSSteerRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that steer request is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the steer request exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued				

UCA-7.5.1	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSSteerRequest too late when ADS is enabled, there is a significant obstacle(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works), or a VRU in the lane of the CAV and adjacent lanes are available /free of obstacles	H-1,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided ADSSteerRequest at the right time	following the control algorithm to provide ADSSteerRequest	ADSSteerRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSSteerRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
					The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation	There was a delay in the update of ADSSteerStatus feedback.	Delayed Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of steer implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSSteerStatus.
					SteerStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSSteerStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
					Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSSteerStatus was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSSteerStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of SteerStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
					AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSSteerStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSSteerStatus exceeds a defined threshold value,appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data. <i>Note: The feedback signals must be processed in a timely manner to detect obstacles correctly even when there are occlusions/other vehicles ahead. False detections must be flagged.</i>	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
				AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no obstacles in the lane of the CAV and there are obstacles in adjacent lanes	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)				
	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) due to communication delays				
	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) within a specified duration of time to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued				

UCA-7.5.2	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSSteerRequest too late when ADS is enabled, a VRU suddenly appears, moving towards the path of the CAV, there are no obstacles on the adjacent lane and maximum deceleration is insufficient to avoid a collision with the VRU.	H-3	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide ADSSteerRequest	<p>The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSSteerRequest is flawed. <i>Note: The control algorithm must cater for steady braking in the ego lane in a timely manner when there is no response to take over request issued upon exit of ODD</i></p>	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue steer request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications		
				<p>The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSSteerRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.</p>	Processing Delay	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that steer request is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the steer request exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued		
				<p>ADSSteerRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.</p>	Communication Delay	The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSSteerRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued		
				<p>The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.</p>	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.		
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	<p>There was a delay in the update of ADSSteerStatus feedback.</p>	Delayed Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of steer implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSSteerStatus.	
					<p>SteerStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSSteerStatus was not received on time.</p>	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSSteerStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued	
					<p>Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSSteerStatus was not updated on time.</p>	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSSteerStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of SteerStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.	
					<p>AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSSteerStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.</p>	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSSteerStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
				AutonomousDriveController believes that there is no VRU in the CAV path or that there are obstacles on the adjacent lane	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.</p>	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
						<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays</p>	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays
						<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data. <i>Note: There must be no false detections and obstacles must be detected in a timely manner even when there are occlusions</i></p>	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
					AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.</p>	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays</p>	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays						
<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.</p>	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued						
<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.</p>	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)						

			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received on time due to communication delays</p> <p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data. <i>Note: There must be no false detections and obstacles must be detected in a timely manner even when there are occlusions</i></p>	<p>Communication Delay</p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) within a specified duration of time to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) due to communication delays</p> <p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the relative position and speed of objects around the CAV	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.</p> <p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays</p> <p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays</p> <p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
		AutonomousDriveController believes that deceleration is sufficient to avoid collision with the VRU	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.</p> <p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays</p> <p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays</p> <p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the relative position and speed of objects around the CAV	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.</p> <p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received on time due to communication delays</p> <p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) within a specified duration of time to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) due to communication delays</p> <p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the control algorithm to determine the strategy(max deceleration or steering away) for the current circumstances	<p>The control algorithm that determines the strategy to deal with suddenly appearing obstacles is inadequate</p>	<p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to determine how to avoid suddenly appearing obstacles in a safe and timely manner.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the inability of the AutonomousDriveController to avoid suddenly appearing obstacles</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to stop providing Steer request.	<p>The control algorithm that calculates the duration of the steer request is incorrect.</p> <p>AutonomousDriveController stops sending ADSSteerRequest at the correct time, but due to communication delay between the AutonomousDriveController and the Vehicle Actuators, SteerRequest was not received on time.</p>	<p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p> <p>Communication Delay</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue steer request at the right time and for the required duration.</p> <p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the ADSSteerRequest is updated on time.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSSteerRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued</p>

UCA-7.6.1	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSSteerRequest too long when ADS is enabled, weather conditions are adverse (heavy rain/snow/fog/ice on the road), the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve and is too close to the border.	H-2	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has stopped providing ADSSteerRequest.	AutonomousDriveController stops sending ADSSteerRequest at the correct time, but due to degradation of the actuators(Vehicle Motion Controller), it was responding late.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSSteerRequest Status to determine the status of steer request implementation.	The ADSSteerStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of steer implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSSteerStatus.
				Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, the ADSSteerStatus feedback was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSSteerStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of SteerStatus due to sensor degradations and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.
				AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSSteerStatus feedback on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSSteerStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position and the road curvature	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrectly updated, ie it doesn't adequately represent the road curvature/layout.	Delayed Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
				Due to communication delays between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays
				The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is received on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes that is not navigating a sharp turn/bend/curve and is not too close to the border.	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrectly updated.	Delayed Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
				Due to communication delays between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signals from the Sensors were not received on time	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are received on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback signals.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes that time of day and weather conditions are favorable for operation of the ADS	The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) were inadequately updated.	Delayed Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting)
				The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) due to communication delays
The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) were received on time on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the time of day and weather conditions		If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued			
AutonomousDriveController believes so because there is no specific feedback on road surface conditions	There is no feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on road surface conditions.	Missing Feedback		There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on road surface conditions from Sensors.	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify road surface conditions from other available sources.		

UCA-7.7.1	AutonomousDriveController stops providing ADSSteerRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, there is a significant obstacle(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works) or a VRU in the lane of the CAV, adjacent lanes are available /free of obstacles and an imminent collision risk prevails.	H-1,2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that it is continuing to provide ADSSteerRequest.	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the steer request anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be able to continuously process steer request when required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to control algorithm degradation	
				AutonomousDriveController is degraded and hence ADSSteerRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide steer request continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController	
				ADSSteerRequest was being issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, SteerRequest was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators	
				ADSSteerRequest was still being issued, but due to actuator degradations, the SteerRequest was not issued anymore.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously implemented upon request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to degradation of the actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators	
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation.	The ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the steer implementation status.	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of steer request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect ADSSteerStatus.
					Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, the ADSSteerStatus feedback was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSSteerStatus is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSSteerStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators
					Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, the ADSSteerStatus feedback was not correctly sent anymore.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the ADSSteerStatus feedback is continuously received.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSSteerStatus due to sensor degradations
					AutonomousDriveController receives correct ADSSteerStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process ADSSteerStatus continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process ADSSteerStatus .
			AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS has been disabled/Driver has taken over control of the DDT.	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller	The DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverOverrideStatus shall be updated on time to indicate correctly whether the Driver has overridden the ADS requests or not	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrectly updated DriverOverrideStatus
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated correctly	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between Maps and AutonomousDriveController	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps.
					AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated correctly
The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between V2X and AutonomousDriveController	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is continuously propagated.				There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X.		

			AutonomousDriveController believes that the CAV has evaded the obstacle/it is no longer in the CAV path/lane and there are obstacles in the adjacent lane.	objects around the CAV(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works)	AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)continuously to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works)	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works)and lane markings/boundaries		The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)shall be updated correctly	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
					Correct feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were issued by Sensors, but due to degradation in the communication channel between Sensors and AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signals were not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
					AutonomousDriveController receives correct feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signals anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) continuously to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works)and lane markings/boundaries	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signals (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc).
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the sensor fusion algorithm to determine the forward road scene		The sensor fusion algorithm that matches sensor data is degraded	Control Algorithm Degradation	The sensor fusion algorithm shall be able to accurately match sensor data to determine the forward road scene
			AutonomousDriveController believes that it is continuing to provide ADSSteerRequest.	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide steer request.	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the steer request anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be able to continuously process steer request when required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to control algorithm degradation
					AutonomousDriveController is degraded and hence ADSSteerRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide steer request continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController
					ADSSteerRequest was being issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, SteerRequest was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators
					ADSSteerRequest was still being issued, but due to actuator degradations, the SteerRequest was not issued anymore.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously implemented upon request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to degradation of the actuator between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators
				AutonomousDriveControllerbelieves that because it was referring to the ADSSteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation.	The ADSSteerStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the steer implementation status.	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSSteerStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of steer request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect ADSSteerStatus.
					Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators, the ADSSteerStatus feedback was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSSteerStatus is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSSteerStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators
					Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, the ADSSteerStatus feedback was not correctly sent anymore.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the ADSSteerStatus feedback is continuously received.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ADSSteerStatus due to sensor degradations
					AutonomousDriveController receives correct ADSSteerStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process ADSSteerStatus continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process ADSSteerStatus .
UCA-7.7.2	AutonomousDriveController stops providing ADSSteerRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, the CAV is continuing to maneuver a	H-2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS has been disabledADS has	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller	The DriverOverrideStatus from Vehicle Motion Controller was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverOverrideStatus shall be updated on time to indicate correctly whether the Driver has overridden the ADS requests or not	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrectly updated DriverOverrideStatus

	<p>sharp turn/bend/curve.</p>		<p>been disabled/Driver has taken over control of the DDT.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV</p>	<p>The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing</p>	<p>Missing Feedback</p>	<p>There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has already navigated the sharp bend/curve.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the road curvature</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.</p> <p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between Maps and AutonomousDriveController</p> <p>AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>Communication Degradation</p> <p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated correctly</p> <p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is continuously propagated.</p> <p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)continuously</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has already navigated the sharp bend/curve.</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(slow speed zone, roadworks, decelerating lead vehicle etc.)</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.</p> <p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received anymore due to degradation in the communication channel between V2X and AutonomousDriveController</p> <p>AutonomousDriveController receives the correct feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData), but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the signal anymore.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>Communication Degradation</p> <p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated correctly</p> <p>The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be well maintained, ensuring that the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is continuously propagated.</p> <p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be able to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)continuously to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV(eg: parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works)</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to process feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the sensor fusion algorithm to determine the forward road scene</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the sensor fusion algorithm to determine the forward road scene</p>	<p>The sensor fusion algorithm that matches sensor data is degraded</p>	<p>Control Algorithm Degradation</p>	<p>The sensor fusion algorithm shall be able to accurately match sensor data to determine the forward road scene</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the inability of the AutonomousDriveController to accurately match sensor data</p>
	<p>UCA-8.1.1</p>	<p>H-3</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided throttle Request</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide throttle request</p>	<p>The control algorithm within AutonomousDriveController that sends throttle request is incorrect</p> <p>AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSThrottleRequest was not sent out.</p> <p>ADSThrottleRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, however, due to errors in communication between the AutonomousDriveController and the Vehicle Actuators, ThrottleRequest was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.</p> <p>ADSThrottleRequest was sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), ThrottleRequest was not sent out to the Vehicle Actuators.</p>	<p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p> <p>Malfunctioning Controller</p> <p>Communication Error</p> <p>Malfunctioning Actuator</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSThrottleRequest when and only when required</p> <p>AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i></p> <p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.</p> <p>Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.</p>	<p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSThrottleRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued</p>
	<p>AutonomousDriveController does not provide ADSThrottleRequest when the CAV is operating on a highway/motorway, ADS is in a degraded mode performing a MRM to move to a safe stopping location and there are vehicles approaching from behind.</p>		<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided throttle Request</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of throttle request implementation</p>	<p>ADSThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation</p> <p>Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSThrottleStatus is sent</p> <p>Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSThrottleStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p> <p>Communication Error</p>	<p>The ADSThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.</p> <p>Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.</p> <p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSThrottleStatus signals.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators</p>

				Correct ADSThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSThrottleStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that it should not send throttle request	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it has correctly followed the control algorithm not to send throttle request.	The specified control algorithm that determines when to send throttle request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine when ADSThrottleRequest must be issued	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSThrottleRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that a safe stopping location has been reached	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the controller logic to determine that a safe stopping location had been reached	The control algorithm that determines whether a safe stopping location has been reached is faulty	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine whether a safe stopping location has been reached	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to determine whether a safe stopping location has been reached or not.
		AutonomousDriveController believes that its not performing a minimum risk manoeuvre	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it followed the controller logic to determine the mode and behavior in that mode	The Control algorithm that determines the mode of operation of ADS and the expected behaviour in that mode is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on the criteria for a safe stopping location	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify a safe stopping location from other available sources.
				Feedback must be included in the design to inform the AutonomousDriveController of the criteria for a safe stopping location.	Missing Feedback	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly determine the mode/status of operation of the ADS and execute appropriate actions.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure of the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm to determine the mode/status of operation of the ADS and execute appropriate actions
				The control algorithm that calculates throttle request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSThrottleRequest when and only when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSThrottleRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide throttle request.	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
		AutonomousDriveController believes that the throttle request provided was correct.	ADSThrottleRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, ThrottleRequest was incorrectly received by the Vehicle Actuators.		Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
			ADSThrottleRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), ThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.		Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued
			ADSThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation		Inadequate Feedback	The ADSThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSThrottleStatus signals.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSThrottleStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued
				Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSThrottleStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators
				Correct ADSThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSThrottleStatus, it shall notify the Driver.
				The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting)
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the time of day, weather conditions and road conditions	Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, Ambient lighting) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
				The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, AmbientLighting) were not received/incorrectly received due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController,	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors

UCA-8.2.1	AutonomousDriveController provides incorrect(excessive) ADSThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled,weather conditions are adverse(rain/snow/fog/ice on road) and there are lead vehicles on the CAV path.	H-3	AutonomousDriveController believes that the throttle request provided is appropriate for the weather conditions	The feedback signals from Sensors (Temperature, Humidity, Ambient lighting)were correctly received, but were misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature,Humidity,AmbientLighting) to to determine the time of day , weather conditions and road conditions	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (Temperature,Humidity,AmbientLighting)accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on the road surface conditions	There is no feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on road surface conditions	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on road surface conditions from Sensors.	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify road surface conditions from other available sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because there is no feedback/input on the throttle performance requirements in adverse weather conditions	The design must include adequate feedback/inputs on throttle performance in adverse weather conditions	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController on the expected throttle performance in adverse weather conditions	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify the expected throttle performance in adverse weather conditions from some other sources
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) to determine the presence/relative position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. Note: The distance to the objects and their relative position/speed are miscalculated based on the feedback signals from the sensors	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no lead vehicles in the CAV path	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
				Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
				Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
				The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
				V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
				Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. Note: The distance to the objects and their relative position/speed are miscalculated based on the feedback signals from V2X	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.		If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.			
			The control algorithm that calculates throttle request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSThrottleRequest when and only when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSThrottleRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.	

UCA-8.2.2	AutonomousDriveController provides incorrect(excessive) ADSThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled and the CAV current speed is the maximum allowed for the zone of operation.	H-4	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide throttle request.	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver	
				ADSThrottleRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, ThrottleRequest was incorrectly received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				ADSThrottleRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), ThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued	
				ADSThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSThrottleStatus signals.	
				Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSThrottleStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued	
				Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSThrottleStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	Correct ADSThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSThrottleStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the CAV speed	The IMUData feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The IMUData feedback signal shall indicate accurate IMU data	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous IMUData
					The WheelSpeed feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelSpeed feedback signal shall indicate accurate wheel speed	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelSpeed
					Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were issued by Sensors, but due to a communication error between Sensors and Autonomous Drive Controller, the signals were not correctly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
					Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing IMUData & WheelSpeed to determine the actual vehicle speed	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process IMUData & WheelSpeed, it shall notify the Driver
					Sensors are malfunctioning, hence feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	Sensors shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback signal shall indicate accurate 6DOF position and orientation	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous 6DOFPosition&Orientation
					The WheelRotations feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelRotations feedback signal shall indicate accurate value of wheel rotations	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelRotations
					AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the speed limit for the current zone/road	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.
Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued					
Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors					

					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The speed limit determined based on the processing of these input signals may be incorrect</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the speed limit for the current zone/road	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.			
UCA-8.2.3	AutonomousDriveController provides incorrect (insufficient) ADSThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV current speed is far below the maximum speed for the current zone of operation and there are vehicles approaching from behind. <i>Note: This may lead to rear-end collision</i>	H-3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes that the throttle request provided was correct.	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide throttle request.	The control algorithm that calculates throttle request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSThrottleRequest when and only when required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSThrottleRequest when required, it shall notify the Driver.			
					AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver			
					ADSThrottleRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, however due to errors in communication between AutonomousDriveController & VehicleActuators, ThrottleRequest was incorrectly received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators			
					ADSThrottleRequest was correctly sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), ThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued			
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	ADSThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSThrottleStatus signals.			
					Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSThrottleStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued			
					Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSThrottleStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators			
					Correct ADSThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSThrottleStatus, it shall notify the Driver.			
			UCA-8.2.3	AutonomousDriveController provides incorrect (insufficient) ADSThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV current speed is far below the maximum speed for the current zone of operation and there are vehicles approaching from behind. <i>Note: This may lead to rear-end collision</i>	H-3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the CAV speed	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the CAV speed	The IMUData feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The IMUData feedback signal shall indicate accurate IMU data	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous IMUData
								The WheelSpeed feedback from Sensors is incorrect.	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelSpeed feedback signal shall indicate accurate wheel speed	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelSpeed
								Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were issued by Sensors, but due to a communication error between Sensors and Autonomous Drive Controller, the signals were not correctly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
								Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing IMUData & WheelSpeed to determine the actual vehicle speed	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process IMUData & WheelSpeed, it shall notify the Driver
								Sensors are malfunctioning, hence feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	Sensors shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
								The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback signal shall indicate accurate 6DOF position and orientation	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous 6DOFPosition&Orientation
The WheelRotations feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The WheelRotations feedback signal shall indicate accurate value of wheel rotations						There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelRotations			
The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.						There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)			

			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the speed limit for the current zone/road	<p>Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p> <p>The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the presence/position of objects around the CAV	<p>Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Communication Error</p> <p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that there are no fast-moving vehicles approaching the CAV	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The speed limit determined based on the processing of these input signals may be incorrect.</i></p> <p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p> <p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the speed limit for the current zone/road</p> <p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSThrottleRequest	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide throttle request.	<p>V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p> <p>The quality of the V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	<p>Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Communication Error</p> <p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSThrottleRequest	<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The distance to the objects and their relative position/speed are miscalculated based on the feedback signals from V2X</i></p> <p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p> <p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.</p> <p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide throttle request.	<p>The control algorithm that sends ADSThrottleRequest is incorrect</p> <p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p> <p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSThrottleRequest when and only required</p> <p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSThrottleRequest when required or issues ADSThrottleRequest when not required, it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	<p>AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSThrottleRequest was fault-issued. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i></p> <p>Malfunctioning Controller</p> <p>AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i></p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSThrottleRequest	<p>ADSThrottleRequest was not sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), ThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.</p> <p>Malfunctioning Actuator</p> <p>Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	<p>ADSThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>The ADSThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSThrottleStatus signals.</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	<p>Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSThrottleStatus is sent</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p> <p>Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	<p>Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSThrottleStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Communication Error</p> <p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	<p>Correct ADSThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.</p> <p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p> <p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus adequately</p> <p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSThrottleStatus, it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the speed limit for the current zone/road	<p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are incorrect</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)</p>

UCA-8.3.1	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSThrottleRequest when the CAV is operating on a motorway / jammed highway ramp/dense urban road, ADS is enabled, and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle(eg: stationary vehicle, blocked lane of travel, decelerating lead vehicle, vehicle cutting in etc.)/or a VRU in its path.	H-1,3	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.
				The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
				Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
				Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
				The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
				The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).
				V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued
				Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X
				The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The relative position of obstacles/VRUs calculated by the AutonomousDriveController may be inaccurate.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSThrottleRequest	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide throttle request.	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSThrottleRequest	The control algorithm that sends ADSThrottleRequest is incorrect
AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSThrottleRequest was fault-issued. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver				
ADSThrottleRequest was not sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), ThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued				
ADSThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSThrottleStatus signals.				
AutonomousDriveController	Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSThrottleStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued			

UCA-8.3.2	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled, the CAV is approaching a red traffic light or a pedestrian crossing and there are VRUs crossing the road	H-1,3,4	believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController,ADSThrottleStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				Correct ADSThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSThrottleStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Sensors to determine the presence / relative position and speed of objects around the CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)	
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued	
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The traffic light colour must be adequately detected even there is dust/dirt over it. The VRUs actions must be predictable based on their relative position, movements and orientation.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.	
			AutonomousDriveController believes that it is not approaching a red traffic light or pedestrian crossing with VRUs	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).
					Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued
					Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the the presence / relative position and speed of objects around the CAV	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the the presence / relative position and speed of objects around the CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from from the V2X (V2XObjectData).			
		V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued			
		Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X			
		The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController. <i>Note: The traffic light colour must be adequately detected even there is dust/dirt over it. The VRUs actions must be predictable based on their relative position, movements and orientation.</i>	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV and predict their movements.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.			
			The control algorithm that sends ADSThrottleRequest is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall correctly issue ADSThrottleRequest when and only required	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to issue ADSThrottleRequest when required or issues ADSThrottleRequest when not required, it shall notify the Driver.		

UCA-8.3.3	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSThrottleRequest when the CAV is approaching a slower speed zone and there are obstacles(eg: decelerating vehicles) ahead.	H-4,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that it has not provided ADSThrottleRequest	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to not provide throttle request.	AutonomousDriveController is malfunctioning, hence, ADSThrottleRequest was fault-issued. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	Malfunctioning Controller	AutonomousDriveController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of AutonomousDriveController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				ADSThrottleRequest was not sent by AutonomousDriveController, but due to the malfunctioning actuator (VehicleMotionController), ThrottleRequest was incorrectly sent to the Vehicle Actuators.	Malfunctioning Actuator	Quality of the actuator from AutonomousDriveController to Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed to ensure that it propagates the appropriate command when required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuators and appropriate notifications issued	
				ADSThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ADSThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ADSThrottleStatus signals.	
				Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence incorrect ADSThrottleStatus is sent	Malfunctioning Sensor	Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued	
				Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController,ADSThrottleStatus is incorrectly received by AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators	
				Correct ADSThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus adequately	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process ADSThrottleStatus, it shall notify the Driver.	
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to ADSThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of the throttle request implementation	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)	
				Sensors are malfunctioning, hence the feedback signals (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) were never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued	
				Due to communication errors between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback from the Sensors were never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors	
				The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) are correct, but they are misinterpreted or improperly processed by the AutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine speed limits, relative position,and speed of objects around the CAV	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.	
				The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Map (MapImage).	
				Map module is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (MapImage) was never sent/incorrectly sent.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the Maps shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate MapImage feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Maps and appropriate notifications issued	
AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	Due to communication errors between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps				
	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) adequately to determine the CAV position	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage), it shall notify the Driver.				
	AutonomousDriveController believes that the throttle request / current vehicle speed is appropriate for the circumstances	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the V2X (V2XObjectData).			
V2X is malfunctioning, hence the feedback signal (V2XObjectData) was never sent/incorrectly sent.		Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of the V2X shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate V2XObjectData feedback signal is sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the V2X and appropriate notifications issued				

			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to detect speed limit signs, presence / relative position, and speed of objects around the CAV</p>	<p>Due to communication errors between V2X & AutonomousDriveController, feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was never received/incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController.</p>	<p>Communication Error</p>	<p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall be guaranteed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X</p>
				<p>The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) is correct, but it is misinterpreted or improperly processed by theAutonomousDriveController.</p>	<p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData) adequately to determine speed limits, presence / relative position, and speed of objects around the CAV.</p>	<p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signal from V2X (V2XObjectData), it shall notify the Driver.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine vehicle speed</p>	<p>The IMUData feedback from Sensors is incorrect.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The IMUData feedback signal shall indicate accurate IMU data</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous IMUData</p>
				<p>The WheelSpeed feedback from Sensors is incorrect.</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The WheelSpeed feedback signal shall indicate accurate wheel speed</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelSpeed</p>
				<p>Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were issued by Sensors, but due to a communication error between Sensors and Autonomous Drive Controller, the signals were not correctly received.</p>	<p>Communication Error</p>	<p>Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors</p>
				<p>Correct feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were received but misinterpreted by the flawed control algorithm of the AutonomousDriveController</p>	<p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p>	<p>The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing IMUData & WheelSpeed to determine the actual vehicle speed</p>	<p>If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process IMUData & WheelSpeed, it shall notify the Driver</p>
				<p>Sensors are malfunctioning, hence feedback signals (IMUData & WheelSpeed) were never sent/incorrectly sent.</p>	<p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p>	<p>Sensors shall be free of malfunctions at all times.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver</p>
				<p>The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The 6DOFPosition&Orientation feedback signal shall indicate accurate 6DOF position and orientation</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous 6DOFPosition&Orientation</p>
				<p>The WheelRotations feedback from Vehicle Actuators is incorrect</p>	<p>Inadequate Feedback</p>	<p>The WheelRotations feedback signal shall indicate accurate value of wheel rotations</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous WheelRotations</p>
		<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that it has provided ADSThrottleRequest at the right time</p>	<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide ADSThrottleRequest</p>	<p>The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSThrottleRequest is flawed.</p>	<p>Faulty Control Algorithm</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue throttle request at the right time and for the required duration.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications</p>
				<p>The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ADSThrottleRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.</p>	<p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that throttle request is issued at the right time</p>	<p>If the processing time for the calculation of the throttle request exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>
				<p>ADSThrottleRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.</p>	<p>Communication Delay</p>	<p>The communication delay between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ADSThrottleRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued</p>
				<p>The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators was degraded, causing a delay in implementing the command.</p>	<p>Actuator Degradation</p>	<p>The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation</p>	<p>The ADSThrottleStatus feedback was delayed.</p>	<p>Delayed Feedback</p>	<p>The ADSThrottleStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of throttle implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSThrottleStatus.</p>
				<p>ThrottleStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & AutonomousDriveController, ADSThrottleStatus was not received on time.</p>	<p>Communication Delay from Controlled Process to Controller</p>	<p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ADSThrottleStatus due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued</p>
				<p>Correct ThrottleStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, ADSThrottleStatus was not updated on time.</p>	<p>Sensor Degradation</p>	<p>The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSThrottleStatus is updated on time.</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of ADSThrottleStatus due to sensor degradations and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.</p>
			<p>AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSThrottleStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.</p>	<p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus within a specified duration of time.</p>	<p>If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSThrottleStatus exceeds a defined threshold value,appropriate notifications shall be issued</p>	

UCA-8.5.1	<p>AutonomousDriveController provides ADSThrottleRequest too late when ADS is enabled, the CAV has entered a higher speed zone, the current vehicle speed is far below the maximum speed for the current zone of operation, there are no obstacles ahead of the CAV and there are accelerating vehicles approaching from behind. <i>Note: This may lead to rear-end collision</i></p>	H-3,4	AutonomousDriveController believes that ADS is not enabled/Driver is in control of the DDT	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to EnableAD to determine the ADS status.	The EnableAD command from HMI was delayed.	Delayed Control Input	The EnableAD command from HMI shall be received by the Autonomous Drive Controller within a specified duration once the Driver has requested for activation of ADS.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays in issuing EnableAD.
				AutonomousDriveController believes that because there is no feedback on which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The feedback to AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV is missing	Missing Feedback	There shall be feedback to the AutonomousDriveController regarding which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV	The AutonomousDriveController shall be able to identify which entity is in control(Driver or ADS) of the CAV from other available sources.
			AutonomousDriveController believes that the throttle request provided is appropriate for the current road/zone of operation	AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from Sensors to determine the speed for the current road/zone of operation and the relative speed and position of vehicles around CAV	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to performance limitations owing to adverse weather and time of day
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) due to communication delays
					The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) were received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays
					The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from V2X to determine the relative speed and position of vehicles around CAV	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData)	
				The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was not received on time due to communication delays	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and V2X shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) due to communication delays	
The feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) was received on time, but there was a delay in processing the data.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) within a specified duration of time.		If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the feedback signal from the V2X (V2XObjectData) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued				
AutonomousDriveController believes that it has stopped providing ADSThrottleRequest.	AutonomousDriveController stops sending ADSThrottleRequest at the correct time, but due to communication delay between the AutonomousDriveController and the Vehicle Actuators, ThrottleRequest was not received on time.	The control algorithm that calculates the duration of throttle request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The AutonomousDriveController control algorithm shall issue throttle request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the AutonomousDriveController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications			
		AutonomousDriveController stops sending ADSThrottleRequest at the correct time, but due to degradation of the actuators(Vehicle Motion Controller), it was responding late.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(VehicleMotionController) between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators and notifications and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.			

UCA-8.6.1	AutonomousDriveController provides ADSThrottleRequest too long when ADS is enabled and the CAV is maneuvering a bend/sharp curve or around a static obstacle in its path.	H-2,3	AutonomousDriveController believes that because it was referring to the ADSThrottleStatus to determine the status of throttle request implementation.	The ADSThrottleStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback	The ADSThrottleStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of throttle implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSThrottleStatus.	
				Correct ThrottleStatus feedback was issued, but due to sensor degradations, the ADSThrottleStatus feedback was not updated on time.	Sensor Degradation	The sensor between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSThrottleStatus is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of ADSThrottleStatus due to sensor degradations and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.	
				AutonomousDriveController received updated ADSThrottleStatus feedback on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing ADSThrottleStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process ADSThrottleStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
			AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signal from Maps to determine the CAV position and the road curvature	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is incorrectly updated, ie it doesn't adequately represent the road curvature/layout.	Delayed Feedback	The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual position of the CAV	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signal from the Map (MapImage)	
				Due to communication delays between Maps & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) was not received on time	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Maps shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) due to communication delays	
				The feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) is received on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signal from the Map (MapImage) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
				AutonomousDriveController believes so because it was referring to the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) to determine the presence/relative position of objects around the CAV and lane markings/boundaries	The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are incorrectly updated.	Delayed Feedback	The feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) shall be updated on time to indicate the actual status of presence/position of objects around the CAV with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc)
			Due to communication delays between Sensors & AutonomousDriveController, the feedback signals from the Sensors were not received on time		Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated feedback signals from Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) due to communication delays	
			The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) are received on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback signals.		Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) within a specified duration of time to accurately determine the presence / position of objects around the CAV.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData, RawImage, etc) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
			UCA-9.1.1	VehicleMotionController does not provide BrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a brake request and the CAV is in a situation where deceleration is required(approaching a slow speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.).	H-1,2,3,4	VehicleMotionController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide brake request	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends brake request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm
VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, BrakeRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times.					There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued	
BrakeRequest was sent by VehicleMotionController, however, due to errors in communication, it was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.					There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators	
VehicleMotionController believes that it should not send brake Request	VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the BrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of brake request implementation	BrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation				Inadequate Feedback	The BrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous BrakeStatus signals.
		Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors it was incorrectly received by VehicleMotionController.				Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators
		Correct BrakeStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by VehicleMotionController.				Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing BrakeStatus adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process BrakeStatus adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued
VehicleMotionController believes that it should not send brake request	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the	The specified control algorithm that determines when to send brake request is incorrect.				Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue BrakeRequest when and only when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of BrakeRequest issued incorrectly
		Although ADSBrakeRequest was issued by Autonomous Drive Controller, due to communication errors it was never received by the VehicleMotionController				Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and VehicleMotionController

UCA ID	Scenario Description	Hazard ID	Vehicle Motion Controller Beliefs	ADS Brake Request Source	Actual Event	Failure Mode	Control Algorithm Behavior	Required Mitigation
UCA-9.2.1	VehicleMotionController provides incorrect BrakeRequest when Driver has provided an override and the CAV is in a situation where deceleration is required (approaching a slow speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.)..	H-1,2,3,4,5	VehicleMotionController believes that the brake request provided was correct.	ADSBrakeRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	ADSBrakeRequest was correctly received by VehicleMotionController, but is misinterpreted by the control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController	Misinterpreted Control Input	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing ADSBrakeRequest adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process ADSBrakeRequest adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide brake request.	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends brake request is incorrect <i>Note: There may be an arbitration error. The algorithm must prioritize Driver requests over ADS requests.</i>	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall prioritize valid driver requests over ADS requests	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of BrakeRequest issued incorrectly
				VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, BrakeRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued	
			VehicleMotionController believes that the brake request provided was correct.	BrakeRequest was sent by VehicleMotionController, however, due to errors in communication, it was not received correctly by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators	
				VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the BrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of brake request implementation	BrakeStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of brake request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The BrakeStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of brake implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous BrakeStatus signals.
				Correct BrakeStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors it was incorrectly received by VehicleMotionController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators	
UCA-9.3.1	VehicleMotionController provides BrakeRequest when ADS is enabled, no brake request has been issued by the Autonomous Drive Controller or the Driver, there are no obstacles or VRUs ahead of the CAV and there are vehicles following closely behind.	H-3	VehicleMotionController believes that it has not provided brake Request	The DriverBrakeRequest was never received due to communication errors	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between the Driver and VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between the Driver and VehicleMotionController.	
				The DriverBrakeRequest was correctly received, but misinterpreted by the control algorithm inside Vehicle Motion Controller	Misinterpreted Control Input	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing DriverBrakeRequest adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process DriverBrakeRequest adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
			VehicleMotionController believes that it must provide brake Request	VehicleMotionController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to not provide brake request	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends brake request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue BrakeRequest when and only when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of BrakeRequest issued incorrectly
				VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, BrakeRequest was fault issued.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued	
UCA-9.5.1	VehicleMotionController provides BrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a brake request and the CAV is in a situation where deceleration is required (approaching a slow	H-1,2,3,4	VehicleMotionController believes that it has provided BrakeRequest at the right time	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue BrakeRequest is flawed.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall issue BrakeRequest at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the VehicleMotionController control algorithm and appropriate notifications must be issued	
				The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue BrakeRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that BrakeRequest is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the BrakeRequest exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
			VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide BrakeRequest	BrakeRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between Vehicle Motion controller and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication delay between Vehicle Motion controller and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received BrakeRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued	
				The BrakeStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback	The BrakeStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of brake implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed BrakeStatus.	

	speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.).			VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the BrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of the brake request implementation	BrakeStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & VehicleMotionController, BrakeStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between Vehicle Actuators & VehicleMotionController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated BrakeStatus(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued
				VehicleMotionController received updated BrakeStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.		Processing Delay	The control algorithm of VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing BrakeStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by VehicleMotionController to process BrakeStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	The ADSBrakeRequest was issued at the right time, but due to a communication delay between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller, it was received late .	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSBrakeRequest
UCA-9.7.1	VehicleMotionController stops providing BrakeRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a brake request and the CAV continues to be in a situation where deceleration is required(approaching a slow speed zone, navigating a sharp turn, at a roundabout or red traffic light, about to collide with an obstacle or a VRU, performing a MRM etc.)	H-1,2,3,4	VehicleMotionController believes that it is continuing to provide brake request.	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide brake request.	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the brake request anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be able to continuously process brake request when required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to control algorithm degradation
					VehicleMotionController is degraded and hence BrakeRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	VehicleMotionController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide brake request continuously due to the degradation of VehicleMotionController
				BrakeRequest was being issued, but due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators,it was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the brake request is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide brake request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators	
				The BrakeStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the brake implementation status.	Inadequate Feedback	The BrakeStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of brake request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect BrakeStatus.	
			VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the BrakeStatus feedback to determine the status of brake request implementation.	Correct BrakeStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators, the feedback was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that BrakeStatus is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated BrakeStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators	
			VehicleMotionController receives correct BrakeStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall be able to process BrakeStatus continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the VehicleMotionController control algorithm to process BrakeStatus .		
			Autonomous Drive Controller is degraded and hence ADSBrakeRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeRequest is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide ADSBrakeRequest continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController		
			VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSBrakeRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	ADSBrakeRequest is issued but not received by the Vehicle Motion Controller due to degradation of the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Motion Controller shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSBrakeRequest is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving ADSBrakeRequest continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Motion Controller	
UCA-10.1.1	VehicleMotionController does not provide SteerRequest when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a steer request and the CAV is in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV, maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a MRM etc.)	H-1,2,3	VehicleMotionController believes that it has provided steer Request	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends steer request is incorrect		Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue SteerRequest when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of SteerRequest issued incorrectly
				VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, SteerRequest was not sent out.		Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances,power supply failure,hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of the VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				SteerRequest was sent by VehicleMotionController, however, due to errors in communication,it was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.		Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionControllerand Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators
			SteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The SteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steer implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous SteerStatus signals.		
			Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors it was incorrectly received by VehicleMotionController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators		
			Correct SteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by VehicleMotionController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing SteerStatus adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process SteerStatus adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued		

			VehicleMotionController believes that Autonomous Drive Controller has not issued a steer request	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSSteerRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	Although ADSSteerRequest was issued by Autonomous Drive Controller, due to communication errors it was never received by the VehicleMotionController	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleMotionController	
					ADSSteerRequest was correctly received by the VehicleMotionController, but is misinterpreted by the control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController	Misinterpreted Control Input	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing ADSSteerRequest adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process ADSSteerRequest adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
UCA-10.2.1	VehicleMotionController provides incorrect SteerRequest when Driver has provided an override and the CAV is in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV, maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve etc.)	H-1,2,3,5	VehicleMotionController believes that the steer request provided was correct.	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide steer request.	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends steer request is incorrect <i>Note: There may be an arbitration error. The algorithm must prioritize Driver requests over ADS requests.</i>	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall prioritize valid driver requests over ADS requests	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of SteerRequest issued incorrectly	
					VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, SteerRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued	
					SteerRequest was sent by VehicleMotionController, however, due to errors in communication, it was not received correctly by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators	
				VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the SteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation	SteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The SteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steering implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous SteerStatus signals.	
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors it was incorrectly received by the VehicleMotionController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators	
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by VehicleMotionController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing SteerStatus adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process SteerStatus adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
				VehicleMotionController believes that Driver has not provided an override	VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the DriverSteerRequest from the Driver	The DriverSteerRequest was never received due to communication errors	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between the Driver and VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between the Driver and VehicleMotionController.
					The DriverSteerRequest was correctly received, but misinterpreted by the control algorithm inside Vehicle Motion Controller	Misinterpreted Control Input	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing DriverSteerRequest adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process DriverSteerRequest adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
UCA-10.3.1	VehicleMotionController provides SteerRequest when ADS is enabled, no steer request has been issued by the Autonomous Drive Controller or the Driver, and there are vehicles or VRUs in adjacent lanes.	H-1,2	VehicleMotionController believes that it has not provided steer Request	VehicleMotionController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to not provide steer request	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends steer request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue SteerRequest when and only when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of SteerRequest issued incorrectly	
					VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, SteerRequest was fault issued.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued	
					SteerStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of steer request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The SteerStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of steering implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous SteerStatus signals.	
				VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the SteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation	Correct SteerStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors it was incorrectly received by VehicleMotionController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators	
					Correct SteerStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by VehicleMotionController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing SteerStatus adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process SteerStatus adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
				VehicleMotionController believes that it must provide steer Request	VehicleMotionController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide steer request	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that determines when to provide steer request is faulty.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue SteerRequest when and only when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of SteerRequest issued incorrectly
VehicleMotionController provides SteerRequest too late when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller			VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide SteerRequest	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue SteerRequest is flawed.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall issue SteerRequest at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the VehicleMotionController control algorithm and appropriate notifications must be issued		
					The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue SteerRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that SteerRequest is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the SteerRequest exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
					SteerRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between Vehicle Motion controller and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication delay between Vehicle Motion controller and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received SteerRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued	

UCA-10.5.1	has issued a steer request and the CAV is in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV and adjacent lanes are free; maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a MRM etc.)	H-1,2,3	VehicleMotionController believes that it has provided SteerRequest at the right time	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the SteerStatus feedback to determine the status of the steer request implementation	The SteerStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback	The SteerStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of steering implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed SteerStatus.
					SteerStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & VehicleMotionController, SteerStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between Vehicle Actuators & VehicleMotionController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated SteerStatus (due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued
					VehicleMotionController received updated SteerStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing SteerStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by VehicleMotionController to process SteerStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSSteerRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	The ADSSteerRequest was issued at the right time, but due to a communication delay between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller, it was received late .	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSSteerRequest
UCA-10.6.1	VehicleMotionController provides SteerRequest too long when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a steer request, weather conditions are adverse (heavy rain, snow, fog or ice on road) and the CAV is maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a MRM etc	H-2	VehicleMotionController believes that it has stopped providing SteerRequest at the right time.	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to stop providing Steer request.	The control algorithm that calculates the duration of the steer request is incorrect.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall issue steer request at the right time and for the required duration.	There shall be a mechanism to detect flaws with the VehicleMotionController control algorithm and issue appropriate notifications
					VehicleMotionController stops sending SteerRequest at the correct time, but due to communication delay it was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the SteerRequest is updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received SteerRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications issued
				VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the SteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation.	The SteerStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback	The SteerStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of steering implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed SteerStatus.
					VehicleMotionController received updated SteerStatus feedback on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing SteerStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by VehicleMotionController to process SteerStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
UCA-10.7.1	VehicleMotionController stops providing SteerRequest too soon when ADS is enabled, ADS has issued a steer request and the CAV is still in a situation where steering is required (eg. Approaching a parked vehicle, blocked lane, road works, or VRU in the lane of the CAV, maneuvering a sharp turn/bend/curve, performing a MRM etc.)	H-1,2,3	VehicleMotionController believes that it is continuing to provide brake request.	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide steer request.	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the steer request anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be able to continuously process steer request when required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to control algorithm degradation
					VehicleMotionController is degraded and hence SteerRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	VehicleMotionController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide steer request continuously due to the degradation of VehicleMotionController
					SteerRequest was being issued, but due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators, it was not received anymore/incorrectly received.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the steer request is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide steer request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators
					The SteerStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the steer implementation status.	Inadequate Feedback	The SteerStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of steering request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect SteerStatus.
				VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the SteerStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation.	Correct SteerStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators, the feedback was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that SteerStatus is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated SteerStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators
					VehicleMotionController receives correct SteerStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall be able to process SteerStatus continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the VehicleMotionController control algorithm to process SteerStatus continuously .
			VehicleMotionController believes that Autonomous Drive Controller has stopped providing steer request	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSSteerRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	Autonomous Drive Controller is degraded and hence ADSSteerRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSSteerRequest is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide ADSSteerRequest continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController
					ADSSteerRequest is issued but not received by the Vehicle Motion Controller due to degradation of the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Motion Controller shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSSteerRequest is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving ADSSteerRequest continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Motion Controller
					The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends throttle request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue ThrottleRequest when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of ThrottleRequest issued incorrectly

UCA-11.1.1	VehicleMotionController does not provide Throttle Request when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a throttle request and there are vehicles approaching from behind.	H-3	VehicleMotionController believes that it has provided throttle Request	VehicleMotionController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide throttle request	VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, ThrottleRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times. <i>Note: Malfunctioning could be caused by factors such as external disturbances, power supply failure, hardware faults etc.</i>	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of the VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					ThrottleRequest was sent by VehicleMotionController, however, due to errors in communication, it was not received by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators
				VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the ThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation	ThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	TheThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ThrottleStatus signals.
			VehicleMotionController believes that Autonomous Drive Controller has not issued a throttle request	VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the ThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of steer request implementation	Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors it was incorrectly received by VehicleMotionController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators
					Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by VehicleMotionController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing ThrottleStatus adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process ThrottleStatus adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSThrottleRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	Although ADSThrottleRequest was issued by Autonomous Drive Controller, due to communication errors it was never received by the VehicleMotionController	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and VehicleMotionController
UCA-11.2.1	VehicleMotionController provides incorrect Throttle Request(excessive) when the Driver has provided an override, weather conditions are adverse(rain/snow/fog/ice on the road), the CAV is very close to the road border and there are lead vehicles on the CAV path.	H-2,3	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide throttle request.	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends throttle request is incorrect <i>Note: There may be an arbitration error. The algorithm must prioritize Driver requests over ADS requests.</i>	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall prioritize valid driver requests over ADS requests	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of ThrottleRequest issued incorrectly	
					VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, ThrottleRequest was not sent out.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued
					ThrottleRequest was sent by VehicleMotionController, however, due to errors in communication, it was not received correctly by the Vehicle Actuators.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators
			VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the ThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of throttle request implementation	ThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ThrottleStatus signals.	
					Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors, it was incorrectly received by the VehicleMotionController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators
					Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by VehicleMotionController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing ThrottleStatus adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process ThrottleStatus adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued
VehicleMotionController believes that Driver has not provided an override	VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the DriverThrottleRequest from the Driver	The DriverThrottleRequest was never received due to communication errors	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between the Driver and VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between the Driver and VehicleMotionController.			
		The DriverThrottleRequest was correctly received, but misinterpreted by the control algorithm inside Vehicle Motion Controller	Misinterpreted Control Input	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing DriverThrottleRequest adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process DriverThrottleRequest adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued			
UCA-11.3.1	VehicleMotionController provides ThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled, no throttle request has been issued by the Autonomous Drive Controller or the Driver, and the CAV is approaching an obstacle(eg: stationary vehicle, blocked lane of travel, decelerating lead vehicle, vehicle cutting in, etc.) or a	H-1,3,4	VehicleMotionController believes that it has not provided throttle Request	The control algorithm within VehicleMotionController that sends throttle request is incorrect	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue ThrottleRequest when and only when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of ThrottleRequest issued incorrectly	
				VehicleMotionController is malfunctioning, hence, ThrottleRequest was fault issued.	Malfunctioning Controller	VehicleMotionController shall be free of malfunctions at all times.	There shall be a mechanism to detect malfunctions of VehicleMotionController and appropriate notifications must be issued	
			VehicleMotionController believes so because it was referring to the ThrottleStatus feedback to determine the status of throttle request implementation	ThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly reflects the status of throttle request implementation	Inadequate Feedback	The ThrottleStatus feedback shall reflect the actual status of throttle implementation.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous ThrottleStatus signals.	
		Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is sent by VehicleActuators, but due to communication errors it was incorrectly received by VehicleMotionController.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and Vehicle Actuators			

	VehicleMotionController believes that it must provide throttle Request		VehicleMotionController believes so because it correctly followed the control algorithm to provide throttle request	Correct ThrottleStatus feedback is received, but it was misinterpreted by VehicleMotionController.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing ThrottleStatus adequately	If VehicleMotionController is unable to process ThrottleStatus adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			VehicleMotionController believes that because it was following the control algorithm to provide ThrottleRequest	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ThrottleRequest is flawed.	Faulty Control Algorithm	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall correctly issue ThrottleRequest when and only when required	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of ThrottleRequest issued incorrectly
UCA-11.5.1	VehicleMotionController provides ThrottleRequest too late when ADS is enabled, Autonomous Drive Controller has issued a throttle request, there are no obstacles ahead of the CAV and there are vehicles following closely behind.	H-3	VehicleMotionController believes that it has provided ThrottlerRequest at the right time	The specified control algorithm that calculates when to issue ThrottleRequest is too complicated and there is a processing delay.	Processing Delay	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall be optimized to ensure that ThrottleRequest is issued at the right time	If the processing time for the calculation of the ThrottleRequest exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				ThrottleRequest was issued at the right time, but due to communication delay between Vehicle Motion controller and Vehicle Actuators, the command was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The communication delay between Vehicle Motion controller and Vehicle Actuators shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly received ThrottleRequest due to communication delays and appropriate notifications must be issued
				The ThrottleStatus feedback was delayed.	Delayed Feedback	The ThrottlerStatus shall be updated to indicate the actual status of throttle implementation with delays not exceeding a specified threshold.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ThrottleStatus.
				ThrottleStatus feedback was issued on time, but due to a communication delay between Vehicle Actuators & VehicleMotionController, ThrottleStatus was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between Vehicle Actuators & VehicleMotionController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated ThrottleStatus (due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued
				VehicleMotionController received updated ThrottleStatus on time, but there was a delay in processing the feedback.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of VehicleMotionController shall be capable of processing ThrottleStatus within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by VehicleMotionController to process ThrottleStatus exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued
				VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSThrottleRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delayed ADSThrottleRequest
UCA-11.7.1	VehicleMotionController stops providing ThrottleRequest too soon when ADS is enabled and providing ADSThrottleRequest, there are no obstacles ahead of the CAV and there are vehicles following closely behind.	H-3	VehicleMotionController believes that it is continuing to provide throttle request.	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController was degraded and therefore unable to issue the throttle request anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The control algorithm inside VehicleMotionController shall be able to continuously process throttle request when required.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide throttle request continuously due to control algorithm degradation
				VehicleMotionController is degraded and hence ThrottleRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	VehicleMotionController shall be well maintained, ensuring that the throttle request is continuously issued when needed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide throttle request continuously due to the degradation of VehicleMotionController
				ThrottleRequest was being issued, but due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators, it was not received anymore.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that the throttle request is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure to provide throttle request continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators
				The ThrottleStatus feedback incorrectly indicates the throttle implementation status.	Inadequate Feedback	TheThrottler Status shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of throttlerequest.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect ThrottleStatus.
				Correct ThrottleStatus feedback was issued, but due to degradation in the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators, the feedback was not received anymore/incorrectly received.	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators shall be well maintained, ensuring that ThrottleStatus is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving updated ThrottleStatus continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between VehicleMotionController and VehicleActuators
				VehicleMotionController receives correct ThrottleStatus, but due to control algorithm degradation, it is unable to process the feedback anymore.	Control Algorithm Degradation	The VehicleMotionController control algorithm shall be able to process ThrottleStatus continuously	There shall be a mechanism to detect failure of the VehicleMotionController control algorithm to process ThrottleStatus continuously .
VehicleMotionController believes that Autonomous Drive Controller has stopped providing throttle request	H-3	VehicleMotionController believes that because it was referring to the ADSThrottleRequest from Autonomous Drive Controller	Autonomous Drive Controller is degraded and hence ADSThrottleRequest is not issued anymore.	Controller Degradations	AutonomousDriveController shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSThrottleRequest is continuously issued when needed in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure to provide ADSThrottleRequest continuously due to the degradation of AutonomousDriveController	
			ADSThrottleRequest is issued but not received by the Vehicle Motion Controller due to degradation of the communication channel between Autonomous Drive Controller and Vehicle Motion Controller	Communication Degradation	The communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Motion Controller shall be well maintained, ensuring that ADSThrottleRequest is continuously propagated.	There shall be a mechanism to detect a failure in receiving ADSThrottleRequest continuously due to degradation of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Vehicle Motion Controller	

UCA-3.1.1	Driver does not provide DriverBrakeRequest when ADS is disabled and the CAV is about to collide with a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path.	H-1,3	Driver believes that they have provided the brake inputs	The user manual/procedure that instructs the Driver how and when to provide brake request is missing in the design	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide braking request.	Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide braking request from some other sources
				DriverBrakeRequest is sent out, but due to communication error between the Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController, the signal is not received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController
				The brake pedal is malfunctioning, hence the braking request was not sent.	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of the actuator (brake pedal) shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator (brake pedal) and appropriate notifications must be issued
				The driver is not competent enough (poor driving skills, knowledge/memory,inadequate training etc.) and hence unable to provide brake request appropriately.	Inadequate Control Input	The Driver must be provided adequate training and it must be ensured that they are capable of taking over and performing DDT at all times.	
			Driver believes that because they were referring to the feedback indicating brake request implementation	DriverBrakeStatus was sent correctly, but due to communication error between VehicleMotionController & Driver Inputs (Brake Pedal), it was not received /incorrectly received	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController
				DriverBrakeStatus was inadequately updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverBrakeStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of driver brake request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DriverBrakeStatus.
			Driver believes that ADS is still enabled and hence there is no need to provide braking inputs.	DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.
				Correct ADMMode was sent from AutonomousDriveController, but due to communication errors between AutonomousDriveController and HMI, the signal is incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI
				The DisplayedADStatus shown on the HMI is too complicated/confusing and it is misinterpreted by the Driver.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall clearly indicate the status of ADS to the Driver such that they can process it in a timely manner	
				Correct ADMMode was received by the HMI, but due to HMI malfunction, DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it displays the appropriate status	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
			Driver believes that there is no collision risk	The user manual does not inform the driver that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status).	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through the user manual/ adequate training/warnings on the HMI	
				The feedback/warning to the driver from the HMI on objects (dynamic and static) too close to the CAV is missing. Note: This is missing in the req/design.	Missing Feedback	There must be HMI feedback to the Driver on objects too close to the CAV posing a collision risk.	The Driver must be made aware of obstacles in the close vicinity of the CAV through other sources
UCA-3.1.2	Driver does not provide DriverBrakeRequest when ADS is disabled and the CAV is approaching a red traffic light signal.	H-4	Driver believes that they have provided the brake inputs	The user manual/procedure that instructs the Driver how and when to provide brake request is missing in the design	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide braking request.	Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide braking request from some other sources
				DriverBrakeRequest is sent out, but due to communication error between the Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController, the signal is not received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController
				The brake pedal is malfunctioning, hence the braking request was not sent.	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of the actuator (brake pedal) shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator (brake pedal) and appropriate notifications must be issued
				The driver is not competent enough (poor driving skills, knowledge/memory,inadequate training etc.) and hence unable to provide brake request appropriately.	Inadequate Control Input	The Driver must be provided adequate training and it must be ensured that they are capable of taking over and performing DDT at all times.	
			Driver believes that because they were referring to the feedback indicating brake request implementation	DriverBrakeStatus was sent correctly, but due to communication error between VehicleMotionController & Driver Inputs (Brake Pedal), it was not received /incorrectly received	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController
				DriverBrakeStatus was inadequately updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverBrakeStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of driver brake request.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DriverBrakeStatus.
			DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.	

			Driver believes that ADS is enabled and hence there is no need to provide braking inputs.	Driver believes that because they were referring to the DisplayedADStatus feedback on HMI to determine whether ADS was enabled or disabled	Correct ADMode was sent from AutonomousDriveController, but due to communication errors between AutonomousDriveController and HMI, the signal is incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI
					The DisplayedADStatus shown on the HMI is too complicated/confusing and it is misinterpreted by the Driver.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall clearly indicate the status of ADS to the Driver such that they can process it in a timely manner	
					Correct ADMode was received by the HMI, but due to HMI malfunction, DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it displays the appropriate status	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
			Driver believes that the CAV is not approaching a red traffic light	Driver believes that because they were not attentive/aware of the driving environment.	The user manual does not inform the driver that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status).	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through the user manual/ adequate training/warnings on the HMI	
UCA-3.5.1	Driver provides DriverBrakeRequest too late when ADS is disabled and the CAV is about to collide with a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path.	H-1,3	Driver believes that they have provided the brake inputs at the right time.	Driver believes that because they thought they had correctly followed the procedure to send braking request.	The specified user manual/procedure that instructs how and when to provide brake is missing/inadequate	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide braking request in a timely manner.	Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide braking request from some other sources
					DriverBrakeRequest is sent out at the right time, but due to a communication delay between the Driver inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController, it was not received on time.	Communication delay	The delays in the communication channel between Driver inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated DriverBrakeRequest(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued
					The Driver Inputs (brake pedal) is degraded, hence DriverBrakeRequest was sent late.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(brake pedal) shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(brake pedal) and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.
					The driver is not competent enough (poor driving skills, knowledge,inadequate training etc.) and hence unable to provide brake request appropriately(at the right time).	Inadequate Control Input	The Driver must be provided adequate training and it must be ensured that they are capable of taking over and performing DDT at all times.	
			Driver believes that the CAV is not approaching or too close to an obstacle or VRU	Driver believes that because there is no feedback to the driver on the static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position.	There is no feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position).	Missing feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position)	The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position) through other sources
					There is no feedback to the driver from the AutonomousDriveController that the driver should be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status). Note: This is missing in the req/design.	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through the user manual/ adequate training/warnings on the HMI	
			Driver believes that ADS is still enabled	Driver believes that because he was referring to the DisplayedADStatus feedback on HMI to determine whether ADS was enabled or disabled	The DisplayedADStatus was inadequately updated.	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.
					ADMode was issued from AutonomousDriverController at the right time, but due to delay in communication between AutonomousDriverController and HMI, the DisplayedADStatus was not updated on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriverController and HMI shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated DisplayedADStatus(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued
					HMI was degraded, hence DisplayedADStatus was inadequately updated.	Sensor Degradation	The HMI shall be well maintained, ensuring that it updates DisplayedADStatus in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the HMI and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.
					Correct DisplayedADStatus was displayed on the HMI, but the information was complicated /confusing, and hence caused delays for the Driver to interpret the information.	Processing Delay	The DisplayedADStatus shall be shown in a clear and intuitive manner such that the Driver can easily process it	
Driver believes that they have provided the brake inputs at the right time.	Driver believes that because they thought they had correctly followed the procedure to send braking	The specified user manual/procedure that instructs how and when to provide brake is missing/inadequate	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide braking request in a timely manner.	Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide braking request from some other sources			
		DriverBrakeRequest is sent out at the right time, but due to a communication delay between the Driver inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController, it was not received on time.	Communication delay	The delays in the communication channel between Driver inputs (brake pedal) and the VehicleMotionController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated DriverBrakeRequest(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued			

UCA-3.5.2	Driver provides DriverBrakeRequest too late when ADS is enabled, there is a takeover request and a load is falling from a truck ahead.	H-3	request.	The Driver Inputs (brake pedal) is degraded, hence DriverBrakeRequest was sent late.	Actuator Degradation	The actuator(brake pedal) shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(brake pedal) and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.				
				The driver is not competent enough (poor driving skills, knowledge,inadequate training etc.) and hence unable to provide brake request appropriately(at the right time).	Inadequate Control Input	The Driver must be provided adequate training and it must be ensured that they are capable of taking over and performing DDT at all times.					
				Driver believes that because there is no feedback to the driver on the static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position.	There is no feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position).	Missing feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position)	The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position) through other sources			
				Driver believes that because there is no feedback to the driver from the AutonomousDriveController that driver should be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status).	There is no feedback to the driver from the AutonomousDriveController that the driver should be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status). Note: This is missing in the req/design.	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through warnings on the HMI or adequate trainings				
				Driver initially believes that there is no transition demand	HMI is degraded, hence, Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings were delayed.	Sensor Degradation	The HMI shall be well maintained, ensuring that Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings are issued/updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings due to HMI degradation and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.			
					Due to communication delays between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController,TakeOverRequest was received too late by HMI, although it was issued on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between HMI and the AutonomousDriveController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated TakeOverRequest(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued			
					TakeOverRequest was received too late .	Delayed Feedback	The Autonomous Drive Controller shall issue TakeOverRequest in a timely manner when required.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed TakeOverRequest			
					The algorithm within AutonomousDriveController which processes the Feedback signals from Sensors(GPSData,RadarData, PointCloud, Raw Images) is too complex and hence there was delay in detecting the load falling from the truck ahead and issuing the TakeOverRequest.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the Feedback signals from Sensors(GPSData,RadarData, PointCloud, Raw Images) within a specified duration of time.	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the Feedback signals from Sensors(GPSData,RadarData, PointCloud, Raw Images) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued			
				UCA-4.1.1	Driver does not provide DriverSteerRequest when ADS is disabled at Night in cold and wet weather (rain)and CAV is in a situation where steering is required (e.g. maneuvering a roundabout, bend/curve).	H-2,3	request.	The user manual/procedure that instructs the Driver how and when to provide steer request is missing in the design	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide steering request.	Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide steering request from some other sources
								DriverSteerRequest is sent out, but due to communication error between the Driver Inputs (steering wheel) and the VehicleMotionController, the signal is not received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Driver Inputs (steering wheel) and the VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (steering wheel) and the VehicleMotionController
The steering wheel is malfunctioning, hence the steering request was not sent.	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of the actuator(steering wheel) shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator(steering wheel) and appropriate notifications must be issued								
The driver is not competent enough (poor driving skills, knowledge/memory,inadequate training etc.) and hence unable to provide steer request appropriately.	Inadequate Control Input	The Driver must be provided adequate training and it must be ensured that they are capable of taking over and performing DDT at all times.									
Driver believes that because they were referring to the feedback indicating steer request implementation	DriverSteerStatus was sent correctly, but due to communication error between VehicleMotionController & Driver Inputs (steering wheel) , it was not received /incorrectly received	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Driver Inputs (steering wheel) and the VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.					There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (steering wheel) and the VehicleMotionController			
	DriverSteerStatus was inadequately updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DriverSteerStatus shall correctly indicate the status of implementation of driver steer request.					There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DriverSteerStatus.			
	DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS					There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.			
Driver believes that ADS is enabled and hence there is no need to provide	Driver believes that because they were referring to the DisplayedADStatus feedback on	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.					There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI			

			<p>Driver believes that steering request is not needed to be provided</p>	<p>Driver believes that because they had referred to the user manual and were not attentive/aware of the driving environment.</p> <p>The Driver believes that because they had not noticed the static/dynamic objects in the vicinity of the vehicle, requiring steering inputs, as their sight is obscured/visibility is poor</p>	<p>The DisplayedADStatus shown on the HMI is too complicated/confusing and it is misinterpreted by the Driver.</p> <p>Correct ADMode was received by the HMI, but due to HMI malfunction, DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated.</p> <p>There is no feedback to the driver that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (Irrespective of ADS Status).</p> <p>The wind screen and/or side view mirrors were not clear/dirty/misty or it was raining and there was no feedback to the driver to clear the wind screen and/or side view mirrors/turn wiper on etc.</p> <p>The ambient lighting is too low /dark outside and there was no feedback to the Driver to turn headlights on.</p> <p>The car cabin was too misty and there was no feedback to the driver to turn demist on.</p>	<p>Misinterpreted Feedback</p> <p>Malfunctioning Sensor</p> <p>Missing Feedback</p> <p>Missing Feedback</p> <p>Missing Feedback</p> <p>Missing Feedback</p>	<p>The DisplayedADStatus shall clearly indicate the status of ADS to the Driver such that they can process it in a timely manner</p> <p>The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it displays the appropriate status</p> <p>The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (Irrespective of ADS Status) through warnings on the HMI or adequate trainings</p> <p>There must be a feedback to the Driver to clear the wind screen and/or side view mirrors/turn wiper on dependent on the environmental conditions</p> <p>There must be feedback to the Driver to turn headlights on when the ambient lighting is too low /dark outside</p> <p>There must be feedback to the Driver to turn demister on when the car cabin is too misty</p>	<p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver</p>
UCA-4.3.1	Driver provides DriverSteerRequest when ADS is disabled and there are vehicles beside the CAV in adjacent lanes or CAV is too close to the central reservation	H-2	<p>Driver believes that they must provide steering input</p> <p>Driver believes that they have not provided steering input</p> <p>Driver believes that there are no vehicles in adjacent lanes, beside the CAV / its not close to the central reservation</p>	<p>Driver believes that because they thought they had followed the user manual on when and how to provide steering inputs</p> <p>Driver believes that because they had followed the procedure not to provide steering inputs.</p> <p>Driver believes that because the vehicles are in the Drivers blind spot and they could not see it</p> <p>Driver believes so because there is no feedback from the Autonomous Drive Controller to the driver on the static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the vehicle and their position</p>	<p>The specified user manual/procedure that instructs how and when to provide DriverSteerRequest is missing/inadequate</p> <p>Driver had not provided steering inputs , but due to malfunctioning Driver Inputs (steering wheel) , DriverSteerRequest is fault issued</p> <p>There is no feedback/warning to the driver to check blindspots for objects</p> <p>There is no feedback from the Autonomous Drive Controller to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the vehicle and their position)/road scene.</p>	<p>Missing Feedback</p> <p>Malfunctioning Actuator</p> <p>Missing Feedback</p> <p>Missing feedback</p>	<p>There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide steering request.</p> <p>The quality of the actuator(steering wheel) shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate command.</p> <p>There must be feedback to the Driver to check for objects in the blindspot.</p> <p>There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position)</p>	<p>Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide steering request from some other sources</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator(steering wheel) and appropriate notifications must be issued</p> <p>The Driver must be made aware of objects in the blindspot through other sources.</p> <p>The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position) through other sources</p>
UCA-4.5.1	Driver provides DriverSteerRequest too late when ADS is disabled, a VRU suddenly appears, moving towards the path of the CAV, there are no obstacles on the adjacent lane and maximum deceleration is insufficient to avoid a collision with the VRU.	H-3	<p>Driver believes that they have provided the steer inputs at the right time.</p> <p>Driver believes that ADS is still enabled</p>	<p>Driver believes that because they thought they had correctly followed the procedure to send steering request.</p> <p>Driver believes that because he was referring to the DisplayedADStatus feedback on HMI to determine whether ADS was enabled or disabled</p>	<p>The specified user manual/procedure that instructs how and when to provide steering request is missing/inadequate</p> <p>DriverSteerRequest is sent out at the right time, but due to a communication delay between the Driver inputs (steering wheel) and the VehicleMotionController, it was not received on time.</p> <p>The Driver Inputs (steering wheel) is degraded, hence DriverSteerRequest was sent late.</p> <p>The driver is not competent enough (poor driving skills, knowledge, inadequate training etc.) and hence unable to provide steer request appropriately(at the right time).</p> <p>The DisplayedADStatus was inadequately updated.</p> <p>ADMode was issued from AutonomousDriverController at the right time, but due to delay in communication between AutonomousDriverController and HMI, the DisplayedADStatus was not updated on time.</p> <p>HMI was degraded, hence DisplayedADStatus was inadequately updated.</p> <p>Correct DisplayedADStatus was displayed on the HMI, but the information was complicated /confusing, and hence caused delays for the Driver to interpret the information.</p>	<p>Missing Feedback</p> <p>Communication delay</p> <p>Actuator Degradation</p> <p>Inadequate Control Input</p> <p>Inadequate Feedback</p> <p>Communication Delay</p> <p>Sensor Degradation</p> <p>Processing Delay</p>	<p>There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide steering request in a timely manner.</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (steering wheel) and the VehicleMotionController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The actuator(steering wheel) shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.</p> <p>The Driver must be provided adequate training and it must be ensured that they are capable of taking over and performing DDT at all times.</p> <p>The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS</p> <p>The delays in the communication channel between AutonomousDriverController and HMI shall not exceed a defined threshold value.</p> <p>The HMI shall be well maintained, ensuring that it updates DisplayedADStatus in a timely manner.</p> <p>The DisplayedADStatus shall be shown in a clear and intuitive manner such that the Driver can easily process it</p>	<p>Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide steering request from some other sources</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated DriverSteerRequest(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the actuator(steering wheel) and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated DisplayedADStatus(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued</p> <p>There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the HMI and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.</p>

			Driver initially believes that there is no VRU in the CAV path	Driver believes that because there is no feedback to the driver on the static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position.	There is no feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the Driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position). <i>Note: There should be warning message on suddenly appearing obstacles/VRUs</i>	Missing feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on suddenly appearing obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path	The Driver must be made aware of suddenly appearing obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path through other sources
				Driver believes that because there is no feedback to the driver from the AutonomousDriveController that the driver should be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status).	There is no feedback to the driver from the AutonomousDriveController that the driver should be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status). <i>Note: This is missing in the req/design.</i>	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through the user manual/ adequate training/warnings on the HMI	
UCA-5.2.1	Driver provides incorrect DriverThrottleRequest when ADS is disabled and the CAV is in a situation where optimal acceleration is needed(moving down a slope and there are leading vehicles in the path.)	H-2,3	Driver believes that they have provided the correct acceleration inputs	Driver believes that because they thought they have correctly followed the user manual/procedure to send acceleration request.	The user manual/procedure that instructs how and when to provide DriverThrottleRequest is missing/ incorrect	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide throttle request in a timely manner.	Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide throttle request from some other sources
					DriverThrottleRequest is sent out correctly, but due to communication error between the Driver Inputs (accelerator pedal) and the AutonomousDriveController, the signal is incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between Driver Inputs (accelerator pedal) and the VehicleMotionController shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between Driver Inputs (accelerator pedal) and the VehicleMotionController
					TheDriver Inputs (accelerator pedal) is malfunctioning, hence DriverThrottleRequest was not correctly sent.	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of the actuator(accelerator pedal) shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator(accelerator pedal) and appropriate notifications must be issued
					The driver is not competent enough (poor driving skills, knowledge,inadequate training etc.) and hence unable to provide acceleration request appropriately	Inadequate Controller	The Driver must be provided adequate training and it must be ensured that they are capable of taking over and performing DDT at all times.	
			Driver believes that there are no lead vehicles in the CAV path	Driver believes that because there is no feedback/warning to the driver on the static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the vehicle and their position/road scene.	There is no feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the Driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the vicinity of the vehicle and their position)/road scene.	Missing feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position)	The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position) through other sources
UCA-5.3.1	Driver provides DriverThrottleRequest when ADS is enabled and the CAV is approaching an obstacle in its path. <i>Note: The driver override in this case may lead to collision</i>	H-3	Driver believes that they must provide acceleration input	Driver believes that because they thought they had followed the user manual on when and how to provide acceleration inputs	The user manual/procedure that instructs how and when to provide DriverThrottleRequest is missing/ incorrect	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to provide throttle request in a timely manner.	Driver must be able to determine when and how to provide throttle request from some other sources
			Driver believes that they have not provided acceleration input	Driver believes that because they had followed the procedure not to provide acceleration inputs.	Driver had not provided acceleration inputs , but due to malfunctioning Driver Inputs (accelerator pedal) , DriverThrottleRequest is fault issued	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of the actuator(accelerator pedal) shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator(accelerator pedal) and appropriate notifications must be issued
			Driver believes that there are no obstacles in the CAV path	Driver believes so because there is no feedback from the Autonomous Drive Controller to the Driver on the static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the vehicle and their position	There is no feedback from the Autonomous Drive Controller to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the vehicle and their position)/road scene.	Missing feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position)	The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position) through other sources
UCA-5.3.2	Driver provides DriverThrottleRequest when ADS is disabled and the current speed is above the maximum limit for the current zone/road	H-4	Driver believes that the current speed is well below the maximum allowed for the current zone/road	Driver believes that because there is no feedback to the Driver on the CAV speed	The specified feedback from the HMI to the Driver regarding CAV speed is missing.	Missing Feedback	There must be a feedback signal to the Driver regarding CAV speed	The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle speed through other sources
			Driver believes that they have not provided acceleration input	Driver believes that because they had followed the procedure not to provide acceleration inputs.	Driver had not provided acceleration inputs , but due to malfunctioning Driver Inputs (accelerator pedal) , DriverThrottleRequest is fault issued	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of the actuator(accelerator pedal) shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate command.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the actuator(accelerator pedal) and appropriate notifications must be issued
	Driver does not provide			Driver believes that because they had followed what they learned from the user manual to activate ADS.	There is no feedback(user manual) to the Driver on the procedure for activation/deactivation of ADS	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources
					The command to activate ADS was not received by the Autonomous Drive Controller due to communication errors between the HMI and the Autonomous Drive Controller.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between the HMI and the Autonomous Drive Controller shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between HMI and the Autonomous Drive Controller.
					The HMI was malfunctioning, hence,EnableAD was not sent from the HMI to the Autonomous Drive Controller.	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate commands	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver

UCA-1.1.1	Driver does not provide HMIEnableAD when the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle or a VRU in its path, the driver intends to activate ADS and has stopped performing the DDT. <i>Note: The Driver may assume that they have already provided it, but the request may not have been actually sent/received by the AutonomousDriveController due to various reasons.</i>	H-1,3,5	Driver believes that they have enabled/activated ADS.	DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.
				Correct ADMMode was sent from Autonomous Drive Controller, but due to communication errors between Autonomous Drive Controller and HMI, ADMMode is incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI
				The DisplayedADStatus information displayed on HMI is too complicated/confusing and it is misinterpreted by the Driver.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall clearly indicate the status of ADS to the Driver such that they can process it in a timely manner	
				Correct ADMMode was received by the HMI, but due to HMI malfunction, DisplayedADStatus was displayed incorrectly to the driver.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it displays the appropriate status	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
UCA-1.1.2	Driver does not provide HMIEnableAD when the CAV is operating on a motorway, another vehicle is cutting into CAV path, the driver intends to activate ADS and has stopped performing the DDT.	H-3,5	Driver believes that they have enabled/activated ADS.	There is no feedback(user manual) to the Driver on the procedure for activation/deactivation of ADS	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources
				The command to activate ADS was not received by the Autonomous Drive Controller due to communication errors between the HMI and the Autonomous Drive Controller.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between the HMI and the Autonomous Drive Controller shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between HMI and the Autonomous Drive Controller.
				The HMI was malfunctioning, hence,EnableAD was not sent from the HMI to the Autonomous Drive Controller.	Malfunctioning Actuator	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it sends the appropriate commands	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.
UCA-1.2.1	Driver provides HMIEnableAD when the CAV is outside its ODD (Eg: heavy snow/rain, poor lighting/poor visibility, failures, a significant object has been detected but not classified and collision is imminent) and Driver has stopped performing the DDT.	H-2,3,5	Driver believes that ADS can be enabled in the current circumstances	Correct ADMMode was sent from Autonomous Drive Controller, but due to communication errors between Autonomous Drive Controller and HMI, ADMMode is incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI
				The DisplayedADStatus information displayed on HMI is too complicated/confusing and it is misinterpreted by the Driver.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall clearly indicate the status of ADS to the Driver such that they can process it in a timely manner	
				Correct ADMMode was received by the HMI, but due to HMI malfunction, DisplayedADStatus was displayed incorrectly to the driver.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it displays the appropriate status	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
				There is no feedback(warning regarding suddenly appearing obstacles and their position).	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on suddenly appearing obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path	The Driver must be made aware of suddenly appearing obstacles/VRUs in the CAV path through other sources
UCA-1.2.1	Driver provides HMIEnableAD when the CAV is outside its ODD (Eg: heavy snow/rain, poor lighting/poor visibility, failures, a significant object has been detected but not classified and collision is imminent) and Driver has stopped performing the DDT.	H-2,3,5	Driver believes that ADS can be enabled in the current circumstances	There is no feedback to the Driver (user manual from the Manufacturer) which provides information on pre conditions for activation of ADS (including the ODD).	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback to the driver on pre conditions for the activation of ADS (including the ODD)	The Driver must be made aware of preconditions for activation of ADS (including the ODD) through other sources
				There is no feedback to the Driver on whether the CAV is outside its ODD or not and hence can be enabled or not.	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback to the Driver on whether the CAV is outside its ODD or not and whether ADS can be enabled or not.	The Driver must be made aware of whether the CAV is outside its ODD or not through other sources.
UCA-1.2.1	Driver provides HMIEnableAD when the CAV is outside its ODD (Eg: heavy snow/rain, poor lighting/poor visibility, failures, a significant object has been detected but not classified and collision is imminent) and Driver has stopped performing the DDT.	H-2,3,5	Driver believes that ADS can be enabled in the current circumstances	There is no feedback to the Driver (user manual from the Manufacturer) which provides information on pre conditions for activation of ADS (including the ODD).	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed of the pre conditions for activation of ADS (including the ODD) through user manual/trainings.	The Driver must be made aware of the pre conditions for activation of ADS (including the ODD) through other sources
				Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings were never issued/incorrectly issued due to malfunctioning HMI	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it issues appropriate Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver

UCA-1.2.2	Driver provides HMIEnableAD when there is a severe ADS/CAV failure and the driver has stopped performing the DDT.	H-5	Driver believes that there are no ADS/CAV failures	Driver believes that because they were referring to the Haptic/Audio/Visual Warnings to determine whether there are any failures	Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning signals are inadequate	Inadequate Feedback	The Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning shall be issued with the expected quality	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly/inadequately issued Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning
					Due to communication errors between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController,the failure signals (SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure) were never received by the HMI	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI
					HMI incorrectly processes /misinterprets the feedback signals from AutonomousDriveController(SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure)	Misinterpreted Feedback	The HMI shall process the failure signals (SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure) adequately	If HMI is unable to process the failure signals (SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure) adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued
					SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure signal was not received/incorrectly received by the HMI	Inadequate Feedback	SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure shall clearly indicate the status of SpeedLimitSignDetection	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure
					LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure was not received/incorrectly received by the HMI	Inadequate Feedback	LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure shall clearly indicate the status of LeadVehicleDistEstimation	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure
					GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure was not received/incorrectly received by the HMI	Inadequate Feedback	GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure shall clearly indicate the status of GNSSBasedLocalisation	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure
UCA-1.5.1	Driver provides HMIEnableAD too late when the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle or VRU in its path, the driver intends to activate ADS and has stopped performing the DDT.	H-1,3,5	Driver believes that they have provided HMIEnableAD at the right time	Driver believes that because they correctly followed the procedure to enable ADS	There is no feedback to the Driver (user manual from the Manufacturer) which provides information on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS.	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources
					The dedicated means/ button to enable/activate ADS was selected/pressed by the driver at the correct time, but due to communication delay between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController, EnableAD was not received on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated EnableAD(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued
					The dedicated means/ button to enable/activate ADS was selected/pressed by the driver at the right time, but due to the degraded HMI, EnableAD was sent too late.	Actuator Degradation	The HMI shall be well maintained, ensuring that it implements the commands as required in a timely manner.	There shall be a mechanism to detect degradations of the HMI and issue notifications to carry out maintenance/replacement.
					Driver believes that because there is no feedback/warning regarding obstacles in the CAV path and their position.	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position).	The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position) through other sources
					Driver initially believes there is no significant obstacle/VRU in its path	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through the user manual/ adequate training/warnings on the HMI	
					Driver believes so because they were not paying attention to the drive environment/road scene ahead	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through the user manual/ adequate training/warnings on the HMI	
UCA-2.1.1	Driver does not provide HMIDisableAD when the ADS is enabled, Driver is not performing the DDT, the CAV is getting close to a significant obstacle or VRU in its path and there is a takeover request due to exit of ODD.	H-1,3,5	Driver believes that they have already deactivated/disabled ADS.	Driver believes that because they were referring to the DisplayedADStatus from HMI to determine the ADS status.	There is no feedback to the Driver (user manual from the Manufacturer) which provides information on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS.	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources
					DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.
					Correct ADMMode was sent from AutonomousDriveController, but due to communication errors between AutonomousDriveController and HMI, the signal is incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI
					The DisplayedADStatus shown on the HMI is too complicated/confusing and it is misinterpreted by the Driver.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall clearly indicate the status of ADS to the Driver such that they can process it in a timely manner	
					Correct ADMMode was received by the HMI, but due to HMI malfunction, DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it displays the appropriate status	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings were never issued/incorrectly issued due to malfunctioning HMI	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it issues appropriate Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
			Driver believes that because they were referring to the	Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning signals are incorrect/ inadequate(The optical signals have inadequate size/contrast,acoustic signals are not loud/clear etc)	Inadequate Feedback	The Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning shall be issued with the expected quality	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly/inadequately issued Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning	

			Driver believes that there is no takeover request	Haptic/Audio/Visual Warnings to determine whether there is a takeover request	Due to communication errors between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController, TakeOverRequest was never received /incorrectly received by the HMI	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI	
					HMI incorrectly processes /misinterprets the TakeOverRequest from AutonomousDriveController and hence Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings are incorrectly issued	Misinterpreted Feedback	The HMI shall correctly process the TakeOverRequest from AutonomousDriveController and issue appropriate Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings	If the HMI is unable to process the TakeOverRequest adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
			Driver believes that they need not deactivate ADS when there is a takeover request.	Driver believes that because they thought they knew how to respond to a take over request	There is no feedback to the driver (user manual) describing the required response to a takeover request.	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed of the expected response to a takeover request through user manual/training.	The Driver must be made aware of the expected response to a take over request through other sources.	
			Driver believes that the CAV is still within its ODD	Driver believes that because there is no feedback to the Driver that the CAV is outside its ODD	There is no ODD exit notification to the Driver included in the design	Missing Feedback	There must be an ODD exit notification included in the design to inform the Driver when the CAV exits its ODD	The Driver must be made aware of exit of ODD through other sources	
UCA-2.1.2	Driver does not provide HMI DisableAD when the ADS is enabled, Driver is not performing the DDT, CAV is operating in a dense urban area, there is a vulnerable road user emerging from behind a parked car and there is a severe ADS/CAV failure (eg: speed limit sign detection failures/GNSS-based localization failures / lead vehicle distance estimation failures).	H-1,5	Driver believes that they have already deactivated/disabled ADS.	Driver believes that because they thought they knew how and when to deactivate ADS from the user manual	There is no feedback to the Driver (user manual from the Manufacturer) which provides information on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS.	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources	
					DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated	Inadequate Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall correctly indicate the status of ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect DisplayedADStatus.	
					Correct ADMode was sent from AutonomousDriveController, but due to communication errors between AutonomousDriveController and HMI, the signal is incorrectly received.	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI	
					The DisplayedADStatus shown on the HMI is too complicated/confusing and it is misinterpreted by the Driver.	Misinterpreted Feedback	The DisplayedADStatus shall clearly indicate the status of ADS to the Driver such that they can process it in a timely manner		
					Correct ADMode was received by the HMI, but due to HMI malfunction, DisplayedADStatus was incorrectly updated.	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it displays the appropriate status	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver	
				Driver believes that because they were referring to the DisplayedADStatus from HMI to determine the ADS status.		Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings were never issued/incorrectly issued due to malfunctioning HMI	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it issues appropriate Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning signals are incorrect/ inadequate(The optical signals have inadequate size/contrast,acoustic signals are not loud/clear etc)	Inadequate Feedback	The Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning shall be issued with the expected quality	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly/inadequately issued Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning	
					Due to communication errors between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController, TakeOverRequest was never received /incorrectly received by the HMI	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI	
					HMI incorrectly processes /misinterprets the TakeOverRequest from AutonomousDriveController and hence Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings are incorrectly issued /not issued	Misinterpreted Feedback	The HMI shall correctly process the TakeOverRequest from AutonomousDriveController and issue appropriate Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings	If the HMI is unable to process the TakeOverRequest adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
					AutonomousDriveController does not have the logic built in to issue a take over request when there is a severe failure	Inadequate Sensor	AutonomousDriveController shall issue a take over request when there is a severe failure	There shall be a mechanism to detect the inability of the AutonomousDriveController to issue a takeover request when there is a severe failure	
				Driver believes that there is no need for disabling ADS		Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings were never issued/incorrectly issued due to malfunctioning HMI	Malfunctioning Sensor	The quality of HMI shall be guaranteed to ensure that it issues appropriate Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of HMI and appropriate notifications must be issued to the Driver
					Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning signals are inadequate	Inadequate Feedback	The Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning shall be issued with the expected quality	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly/inadequately issued Haptic/Audio/VisualWarning	
					Due to communication errors between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController, the failure signals (SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure) were never received by the HMI	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and HMI	
						HMI incorrectly processes /misinterprets the feedback signals from AutonomousDriveController(SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure)	Misinterpreted Feedback	The HMI shall process the failure signals (SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure) adequately	If HMI is unable to process the failure signals (SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure,LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure,GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure) adequately, appropriate notifications shall be issued
			SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure signal was not received/incorrectly received by the HMI	Inadequate Feedback	SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure shall clearly indicate the status of SpeedLimitSignDetection	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous SpeedLimitSignDetectionFailure			

				Driver believes that because they were referring to the Haptic/Audio/Visual Warnings to determine whether there is any failure	LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure was not received/incorrectly received by the HMI	Inadequate Feedback	LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure shall clearly indicate the status of LeadVehicleDistEstimation	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous LeadVehicleDistEstimationFailure	
					GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure was not received/incorrectly received by the HMI	Inadequate Feedback	GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure shall clearly indicate the status of GNSSBasedLocalisation	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous GNSSBasedLocalisationFailure	
					SelfAssessmentStatus was incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	SelfAssessmentStatus shall indicate the status of self assessment of the ADS	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous SelfAssessmentStatus	
					PerceptionReliabilityScore was incorrect	Inadequate Feedback	PerceptionReliabilityScore shall clearly indicate how reliable the perception system is	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous PerceptionReliabilityScore	
					AutonomousDriveController misinterprets/incorrectly processes the signals from Self-Assessment and hence TakeOverRequest was never issued	Misinterpreted Feedback	AutonomousDriveController shall correctly process the signals from Self-Assessment and issue TakeOverRequest if required.	If the HMI is unable to process the signals from Self-Assessment and issue TakeOverRequest when required, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
					ObjectDetectionCheck feedback is incorrect/inadequate	Inadequate Feedback	ObjectDetectionCheck shall indicate the status of object detection of Perception & Localisation accurately	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous ObjectDetectionCheck	
					LocalizationCheck feedback is incorrect/inadequate	Inadequate Feedback	LocalizationCheck shall indicate the status of localisation check of Perception & Localisation accurately	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous LocalizationCheck	
					ObjectTrackingCheck feedback is incorrect/inadequate	Inadequate Feedback	ObjectTrackingCheck shall indicate the status of object tracking of Perception & Localisation accurately	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous ObjectTrackingCheck	
					SensorVisibility feedback is incorrect/inadequate	Inadequate Feedback	SensorVisibility shall indicate the status of visibility of sensors accurately	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous SensorVisibility	
					SensorObstruction feedback is incorrect/inadequate	Inadequate Feedback	SensorObstruction shall indicate the status of obstruction of the Sensors accurately	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous SensorObstruction	
				Driver believes that because they thought they knew when to disable/deactivate ADS	There is no feedback to the driver (user manual) describing when to deactivate ADS	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources	
UCA-2.3.1	Driver provides HMIDisableAD when ADS is enabled, the CAV is within its ODD, there are static obstacles, dynamic obstacles and VRUs in the close vicinity of the CAV and the Driver is not performing the DDT.	H-1,2,3,5	Driver believes that CAV is outside its ODD	Driver believes that because they had assumed they knew the ODD of the CAV	There is no feedback to the Driver (user manual from the Manufacturer) which provides clear/adequate information on the ODD of the CAV and when to enable/disable ADS.	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed of the pre-conditions for activation of ADS (including the ODD) and when to deactivate ADS through training/ user manuals.	The Driver must be made aware of the pre-conditions for the activation of ADS (including the ODD) and when to deactivate ADS through other sources	
					Driver believes that they have not deactivated/disabled ADS.	Driver believes that because there was no feedback to the Driver on the procedure to deactivate/disable ADS	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources
						The HMI design is flawed , it doesn't protect against unintentional deactivation	Flawed Design	The HMI shall protect against unintentional activation/deactivation of ADS by the Driver	There shall be a mechanism to detect unintentional activation/deactivation of ADS by the Driver and appropriate notifications issued
UCA-2.5.1	Driver provides HMIDisableAD too late when there is a request to take over, the driver is not performing the DDT, and there is a load falling from a truck ahead.	H-3,5	Driver believes that they have provided HMIDisableAD at the right time	Driver believes that because they had followed the right procedure to deactivate/disable ADS	There was no feedback(user manual/training) to the Driver on when and how to deactivate ADS.	Missing Feedback	There must be adequate feedback provided to the driver (in the form of user manual or training) on when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner	Driver must be able to determine when and how to activate/deactivate ADS in a timely manner from some other sources	
					HMI is degraded, hence, Haptic/Audio/VisualWarnings were delayed.	Sensor Degradation	The HMI shall be well maintained, ensuring that Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings are issued/updated on time.	There shall be a mechanism to detect delays or failures in the update of Haptic/Audio/Visual warnings due to HMI degradation and notifications issued to carry out maintenance/replacement.	
					Due to communication delays between the HMI and the AutonomousDriveController,TakeOverRequest was received too late by HMI, although it was issued on time.	Communication Delay	The delays in the communication channel between HMI and the AutonomousDriveController shall not exceed a defined threshold value.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrectly updated TakeOverRequest(due to communication delays) and appropriate notifications issued	
					TakeOverRequest was received too late .	Delayed Feedback	The Autonomous Drive Controller shall issue TakeOverRequest in a timely manner when required.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed TakeOverRequest	
					The algorithm within AutonomousDriveController which processes the Feedback signals from Sensors(GPSData,RadarData, PointCloud, Raw Images) is too complex and hence there was delay in detecting the load falling from the truck ahead and issuing the TakeOverRequest.	Processing Delay	The control algorithm of AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the Feedback signals from Sensors(GPSData,RadarData, PointCloud, Raw Images) within a specified duration of time and issue takeover request if required	If the time taken by AutonomousDriveController to process the Feedback signals from Sensors(GPSData,RadarData, PointCloud, Raw Images) exceeds a defined threshold value, appropriate notifications shall be issued	
					GPS Data from Sensors is not updated on time	Delayed Feedback	The Sensors shall issue GPS Data in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed GPS Data	
					PointCloud from Sensors is not updated on time	Delayed Feedback	The Sensors shall issue PointCloud in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed PointCloud	
					RadarData from Sensors is not updated on time	Delayed Feedback	The Sensors shall issue RadarData in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed RadarData	
	RawImage from Sensors is not updated on time	Delayed Feedback	The Sensors shall issue RawImage in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed RawImage					

			Driver believes that there is no load falling from a truck ahead / no risk of collision	Driver believes that because they were not paying attention to the road environment	There is no feedback to the Driver on the HMI that they must be attentive at all times and aware of the driving environment irrespective of the state of ADS	Missing Feedback	The Driver must be informed that they need to be attentive (aware of the driving environment) and available to take over DDT at all times (irrespective of ADS Status) through the user manual/ adequate training/warnings on the HMI	
				Driver believes that because there is no feedback/warning regarding obstacles in the CAV path and their position.	The feedback to the Driver regarding obstacles in the CAV path and their position when there is a collision risk, is missing	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback from the AutonomousDriveController to the driver on the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position)	The Driver must be made aware of the vehicle environment (static and dynamic objects in the close vicinity of the CAV and their position) through other sources
UCA-12.1.1	RemoteOperator does not provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received and verified and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3	Remote Operator believes that they have already provided DynamicPathVerificationResponse	Remote Operator believes that because they thought they had followed the right procedure to provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse	There is no feedback(user manual/training) provided to the Remote Operator on how to provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback(user manuals/training) to the Remote Operator on how to provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse	The remote Operator shall be made aware of how to provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse through other sources
				Remote Operator believes that because they thought they had followed the right procedure to provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse	Although DynamicPathVerificationResponse was provided by the Remote Operator, due to errors in communication between the actuator and the AutonomousDriveController, it was never received by the AutonomousDriveController	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between the actuator and the AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that DynamicPathVerificationResponse is correctly received.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between the actuator and the AutonomousDriveController
				Remote Operator believes that they do not have to provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse after a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received	Remote Operator believes that because they do not know how to respond to a DynamicPathVerificationRequest	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback(user manuals/training) to the Remote Operator on how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received	The remote Operator shall be made aware of how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received through other sources
UCA-12.2.1	RemoteOperator provides DynamicPathVerificationResponse incorrectly when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received but not verified or verified incorrectly and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3	Remote Operator believes that they have provided the right response	Remote Operator believes that because they thought they had followed the right procedure to verify and provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse	There is no feedback(user manual/training) provided to the Remote Operator on how to verify and provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback(user manuals/training) to the Remote Operator on how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received	The remote Operator shall be made aware of how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received through other sources
				Remote Operator believes that because they thought they had followed the right procedure to verify and provide DynamicPathVerificationResponse	Although DynamicPathVerificationResponse was correctly issued by the Remote Operator, due to errors in communication between the actuator and the AutonomousDriveController, it was incorrectly received by the AutonomousDriveController	Communication Error	Quality and integrity of the communication channel between the actuator and the AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that DynamicPathVerificationResponse is correctly received.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between the actuator and the AutonomousDriveController
UCA-12.4.1	RemoteOperator provides DynamicPathVerificationResponse too early when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received but not verified and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3	RemoteOperator believes that they have provided DynamicPathVerificationResponse at the right time	Remote Operator believes that because they thought they had followed the right course of action once DynamicPathVerificationRequest was received.	There is no feedback(user manual/training) provided to the Remote Operator on how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback(user manuals/training) to the Remote Operator on how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received	The remote Operator shall be made aware of how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received through other sources
UCA-12.5.1	RemoteOperator provides DynamicPathVerificationResponse too late when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest has been received and verified and the CAV is approaching a significant obstacle in its path.	H-3	RemoteOperator believes that they have provided DynamicPathVerificationResponse at the right time	Remote Operator believes that because they thought they had followed the right course of action once DynamicPathVerificationRequest was received.	There is no feedback(user manual/training) provided to the Remote Operator on how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received	Missing Feedback	There must be feedback(user manuals/training) to the Remote Operator on how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received	The remote Operator shall be made aware of how to respond / actions to be taken when a DynamicPathVerificationRequest is received through other sources

Annex 5: Safety Requirements

Requirement to Prevent the CF	Requirement to Detect the CF	ODD	HMI	Driver	V2X	Self-Assessment	Sensors	AutonomousDriveController
Quality of the sensor between Vehicle Actuators and AutonomousDriveController shall be guaranteed to ensure that feedback signals are correctly sensed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the sensor and appropriate notifications issued						x	
The feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) shall be accurate.	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of incorrect/erroneous feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData,PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc)						x	
The accuracy and performance of the Sensors shall not be inhibited by adverse weather conditions, poor visibility or occlusions.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the reduction in accuracy or performance of the Sensors and notify the Driver about this.			x			x	
The quality of the Sensors shall be guaranteed to ensure that accurate feedback signals are sent	There shall be a mechanism to detect the malfunctions of the Sensors and appropriate notifications must be issued			x			x	
Quality and integrity of the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors shall be guaranteed.	There shall be a mechanism to detect faults in the communication channel between AutonomousDriveController and Sensors						x	
The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the presence and relative position/speed of objects around the CAV.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.						x	
The accuracy and performance of the Sensors shall not be inhibited by adverse weather conditions, poor visibility, occlusions, etc.	There shall be a mechanism to detect the reduction in accuracy or performance of the Sensors and notify the Driver about this.			x			x	
PerceptionReliabilityScore shall accurately indicate how reliable the perception system is.	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated PerceptionReliabilityScore and appropriate notifications issued						x	
The SensorVisibility shall provide an estimate of sensor effective visibility	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SensorVisibility						x	
The SensorObstruction shall provide an estimate of amount of sensor obstruction	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/inadequately updated SensorObstruction						x	
Self assessment shall process all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck,LocalizationCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) to determine how reliable the perception and localisation systems are	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process all feedback signals from Sensors(SensorVisibility&SensorObstruction) and Perception&Localisation(ObjectDetectionCheck,LocalizationCheck & ObjectTrackingCheck) to generate a reliability score, it shall notify the Driver.					x	x	
The control algorithm inside AutonomousDriveController shall be capable of processing the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) adequately to determine the speed limits for the roads/zones.	If AutonomousDriveController is unable to process the feedback signals from the Sensors (GPSData, PointCloud, RadarData,RawImage, etc) accurately, it shall notify the Driver.						x	

SensorObstruction shall indicate the status of obstruction of the Sensors accurately	There shall be a mechanism to detect incorrect/erroneous SensorObstruction									x	
The Sensors shall issue GPS Data in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed GPS Data									x	
The Sensors shall issue PointCloud in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed PointCloud									x	
The Sensors shall issue RadarData in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed RadarData									x	
The Sensors shall issue RawImage in a timely manner	There shall be a mechanism for the detection of delayed RawImage									x	